

Education Domain Model

System of Concepts to Support Life-Long Learning

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Validation, verification and evaluation

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Ch. 02	+KM	+OS	+MR	+KK	+VP	+GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 03	+KM	+OS	+MR	+KK	+VP	+GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 04	+KM	+OS	+MR	+KK	+VP	+GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 05	+KM	+OS	+MR	+KK	+VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 06	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 07	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 08	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 09	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 10	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 11	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 12	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS
Ch. 13	+KM	+OS	+MR	-KK	-VP	-GP	-MM	-SS

Foreword

In today's world of global mobility, individuals frequently relocate for reasons related to employment, education, housing, and leisure. One of the challenges associated with such mobility is the need to verify one's educational level, knowledge, and skills in new countries, educational institutions, and workplaces, just as it is necessary and beneficial to verify one's medical history and health status.

In medical and health informatics, comprehensive interoperability standards have been developed to facilitate the seamless exchange of Electronic Health Record (EHR) data between healthcare providers and other stakeholders. Similarly, the education sector faces an analogous need, so implementing an Electronic Education Record (EER) focused on integrating educational data and systems seems essential. Comparable to EHRs in the medical and health domains, the EER would function within the education sector by consolidating all data related to an individual's education, knowledge, and skills into a unified, evidence-based, comprehensive, and complete educational record. This record would encompass everything from primary education to higher education studies, further professional training, and the knowledge and skills acquired through work experience. This system supports lifelong learning principles and enables individuals to verify their educational achievements and acquired competencies across different countries and institutions.

The proposed Education Domain Model aims to initiate discussions and associated research focused on defining concepts and terminology within the education sector to ensure consistency and interoperability of data and systems despite differences in education systems and educational data documentation practices. Consistency and interoperability are essential requirements for ensuring the integrity and verifiability of educational records, thereby supporting individuals in demonstrating their qualifications and skills in an increasingly mobile and interconnected world.

The proposed Education Domain Model is not an endpoint but rather the beginning of a journey. With authors drawn from both the education sector and the medical and health domains, we have based the structure and format of this document on the health informatics standard ISO 13940 (Health informatics — System of concepts to support continuity of care), version 15 December 2015.

1 Introduction

1.1 General

The Education Domain Model aims to define the generic concepts needed to achieve continuity in education records. Continuity in education is an essential aspect of quality and reliability in educational services, and semantic interoperability is a requirement for this continuity. The required concepts should represent the content and context of educational services and other education-related activities.

Education is provided through various formal educational institutions, workplace learning, professional development, and self-directed learning. These educational and administrative processes reflect the interaction between learners, educational professionals and other stakeholders. An educational process provides continuity from the learner's perspective. Several basic premises for management, resource handling, and administration are also needed to complete the concepts representing continuity in education.

The system of concepts for continuity in education defined in the Education Domain Model is based upon the educational perspective with the educational process as the focus. It describes its component concepts and their descriptive terms regarding all types of educational services, including formal education, workplace learning, further training, and self-learning, especially considering learner-centred continuity in education. This Education Domain Model will establish a common conceptual framework across national, cultural, and professional barriers.

1.2 Aims and objectives

The Education Domain Model aims to provide a comprehensive, conceptual basis for content and context in educational services and other learning forms. It should be the foundation for interoperability at all levels in educational organizations and related stakeholders and for developing information systems in education.

The concepts aim to support the continuity of education by focusing on educational processes and learning, enabling the use of educational information for other purposes as well, such as anonymised and pseudonymised secondary use for research, policy-making, governmental statistics, and machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) applications like tracking progress and facilitating knowledge management. The core activity in education is the interaction between learners and educational professionals; such interactions occur in educational and administrative processes and justify the process-oriented approach of the Education Domain Model. To represent educational content and context, the Education Domain Model is based on the educational perspective and focuses on the educational process as a central concept for achieving continuity of education through lifelong learning.

Education is provided through various formal educational institutions, workplace learning, professional development, and self-directed learning. By incorporating these diverse forms of learning, the model ensures that all aspects of an individual's educational journey are captured and can be seamlessly integrated and verified across different environments and contexts. To support the continuity of education, the model also aims to include comprehensive concept definitions and concept relations for education's educational, management, and resource aspects. In practice, the Education Domain Model aims to be used whenever requirements for information in education are specified. This will cover all specifications in developing enterprise models for interoperability on international, national, or local levels, information systems, and structured information for specified types of educational processes.

1.3 Concept of education

This Education Domain Model is based on the foundational principles of education: a state of comprehensive cognitive, social, and emotional development and not merely the acquisition of knowledge or skills. Over time, these principles have been refined to describe education as a resource for everyday life, not the objective of living, and to emphasise that education is a positive concept highlighting social and personal resources and intellectual capacities.

The Education Domain Model categorises the concept of education in a detailed manner. The model identifies educational components: learning processes, educational structures, activities and participation, and personal and environmental factors. This Education Domain Model adopts these educational principles as its foundation.

In this Education Domain Model, the term education is not an isolated term designating any concept within the model's scope. Instead, education serves as a prefix in several terms. The meaning of this prefix is that the concept represented by the term relates to the subject's educational state or condition, often in the context of an educational or learning process.

1.4 Formal versus non-formal education

This education domain model is designed to integrate both formal and non-formal education. It supports learning and development through a comprehensive approach with diverse educational activities. Formal and non-formal education contribute to individuals' cognitive, emotional, social, and physical growth, enabling a more inclusive and adaptable learning experience.

Formal education typically involves structured, curriculum-based programs provided by schools, universities, and other accredited institutions. Non-formal education, on the other hand, occurs in more flexible and informal settings, such as community programs, workshops, self-directed learning initiatives, and experiences gained from daily work activities. Despite these differences, the domain model integrates both approaches into a unified framework.

The education domain model emphasizes the interaction between formal and non-formal education by addressing the roles of learners, educators, instructors, mentors, supervisors, etc., across various contexts. Its structure and terminology are intentionally broad, making the model applicable to both education forms. By connecting formal and non-formal learning, this domain model fosters lifelong learning and supports documenting diverse learning activities and outcomes to better meet various stakeholders' needs.

1.5 Intended users of education domain model

All parties interested in the interoperability issues within education are the intended users of this education domain model. This includes but is not limited to educators, instructors, learners, education managers, education funding organizations, all types of education providers, community learning teams, and teams organizing various learning activities in workplaces.

This system of education concepts is relevant across all educational information and the development and use of education-related software systems. It can also be applied to organizational analysis, serving as a foundation for strategic decisions and, more broadly, in initiatives not directly tied to formal education systems.

1.6 Architecture of education domain model

This system of concepts is built upon the perspective of the learning process, which serves as the core element of the education domain. All other areas of work in education relate to and interact with the learning process. For instance, the management aspects of education are represented in the process management areas, while the resource support areas are correspondingly identified as outcomes of the support processes.

What	How	Where	Who	When	Why
Things	Processes	Locations	Persons	Events	Strategies
Products and services	Reporting (feedback)	Organization and organization structure	Persons	Business events	Business rules

Figure 1: Zachman-framwrork based architecture

Architecturally, we follow the Zachman Framework [1], grouping concepts according to the questions: who, what, how, why, when, and where. These questions are addressed using concepts such as people, organisations, and their roles (**who**); products and services (**what**); processes (**how**); rules and prescriptions (**why**); events (**when**); and their locations (**where**) (Figure 1).

In doing so, we adhere to the key principles of domain modelling (*domain facets*) by analysing and modelling the following [2]:

1. The two main business processes of education (*learning and teaching*);
2. Stakeholders (*people, organisations, and roles*);
3. Intrinsic elements (*products and services*);
4. Supporting activities and technologies (e.g. *educational events*);
5. Management and organisation;
6. Rules, regulations, and scripts; and
7. Human behaviour.

1.7 Description and display of concepts

In this education domain model, we follow the pattern in ISO standard 13940 (Health informatics — System of concepts to support continuity of care) [3]. The concepts are organised into distinct sections. The relationships between the educational and informational areas that need to be addressed are used to structure this domain model. Each concept is systematically defined and described, with its relationships illustrated using UML models.

Descriptions are presented in tables following a consistent format, and information is systematically provided for all concepts outlined in the sections. Some categories may intentionally remain blank if irrelevant to a specific concept.

Examples are included where they are deemed useful and necessary. In general, examples of broader concepts are found at the level of their corresponding subordinate concepts.

Diagrams based on UML conventions are included to assist the reader in understanding the relationships between concepts. For each concept described in the sections, a partial view of the overall model is provided, showing only its direct relationships with other concepts relevant to that aspect of the model.

At the beginning of each section, diagrams provide partial views of the following concepts, focusing on the topic addressed in that section. For clarity:

- Concepts shown in white with a solid border are defined in the same section or subsection.
- Concepts defined in other sections or subsections are shown in grey with a solid border.
- Concepts not defined in this model are shown in grey without a boundary line.
- For concepts shown in white, all relationships are included.
- Relationships between concepts shown in grey are not included.
- *Italic characters* are used in headings for concepts that are purely abstract and supported only through their specialisations.

Concept models are used in this education domain model to highlight the relationships between concepts. Attributes are not considered part of concept modelling. Attributes can be added during implementation without conflicting with this domain model.

2 Scope

The proposed education domain model defines a system of concepts for various aspects of education provision. The core activity in formal education is the interaction between learners and educators. Such interactions occur in educational processes and form the basis for the process-oriented approach of this model. To represent educational content and its context, this domain model relates to a generic education process model and comprehensive concept definitions and models for the pedagogical, management, and resource aspects of educational services. In practice, the domain model provides the necessary concept definitions whenever structured information in education is specified as a requirement. The definitions are intended to apply only at the conceptual level without delving into implementation details. This domain model encompasses all levels of specification in the development of:

- logical reference models within the information viewpoint as a common basis for semantic interoperability at international, national, or local levels,
- educational information systems, and
- information for specific types of educational processes.

This domain model does not cover the specifics of performing particular pedagogical or administrative processes. Educational research and training processes are also beyond the scope of this first version of the educational domain model.

3 References

We use the ISO 13940 “*Health informatics standard - System of concepts to support continuity of care*” [3] as a reference when designing and structuring a domain model for education. All terms and definitions are aligned with the ISO 21001 standard “*Management systems for educational organizations — Requirements with guidance for use*” [4]. Where appropriate, we adopt terminology from ISO 21001 within the domain model, mirroring how ISO 13940 incorporates ISO/TS 21298 (Health informatics — Functional and structural roles).

4 Terms and definitions

4.1 Education

4.1.1 Education

Term: *education (healthcare)*

Definition: Teaching and learning activities, services, management, or suppliers related.

NOTE: This includes more than carrying out procedures for students. It also involves, for example, the management of information about students, their learning progress, and interactions within the educational framework and may also encompass the management of pedagogical knowledge.

4.1.2 Continuity of education

Term: *continuity of education (continuity of care)*

Definition: Efficient, effective, and ethical education delivered through interaction, integration, coordination, and sharing of *information* between different educational stakeholders over time.

4.2 Concepts and terms

4.2.1 Concept

Term: *concept (concept)*

Definition: Unit of knowledge created by a unique combination of characteristics within the educational context.

4.2.2 System of concepts

Term: *system of concepts (system of concepts)*

Definition: A set of *concepts* structured according to the relationships among them within the educational framework.

4.2.3 Deprecated term

Term: *deprecated term (deprecated term)*

Definition: A rejected term in the context of education.

4.3 Actors

4.3.1 Organization

Term: *organization (organization)*

Definition: Unique framework of authority within which a *person* or persons act or are designated to act towards some purpose.

NOTE 1: Groupings or subdivisions of organizations may also be considered as organizations where there is a need to identify them in this way for purposes of information interchange.

NOTE 2: In this domain model, this definition applies to any organization, whatever their legal status.

4.3.2 Organizational pattern

Term: *organizational pattern* (*organizational pattern*)

Definition: Relationships between the various parts of an *organization*.

4.3.3 Party

Term: *party* (*party*)

Definition: Person or group performing a *role* concerning the business of a specific community or domain.

4.3.4 Person

Term: *person* (*person*)

Definition: Human being regarded as an individual.

4.3.5 Role

Term: *role* (*role*)

Definition: Function or position.

4.3.6 Person role

Term: *person role* (*person role*)

Definition: A *role* of a *person*.

4.3.7 Organization role

Term: *organization role* (*organization role*)

Definition: A *role* of an *organization*.

4.4 Resources

4.4.1 Resource

Term: *resource* (*resource*)

Definition: A resource that is utilised or consumed during the execution of a *process*.

NOTE 1: This includes various entities such as funding, staff, facilities, capital equipment, tools, and utilities such as electricity, water, fuel, and communication infrastructure.

NOTE 2: Resources encompass reusable, renewable, or consumable.

4.4.2 Educational device

Term: *educational device* (*medical device*)

Definition: A tool or technology specifically designed to support or enhance the teaching and learning process in an educational setting, used to facilitate students' acquisition of knowledge, skills, or competencies.

4.4.3 Educational product

Term: *educational product* (*medicinal product*)

Definition: Any resource, tool, or combination of materials that can be utilised to facilitate students' learning process, enhance knowledge, skills, or competencies, assess educational progress, or support the development of cognitive or behavioural functions within an educational context.

4.5 Management

4.5.1 Quality in education

Term: *quality in education* (*quality in healthcare*)

Definition: The degree to which *education* fulfils requirements related to defined quality characteristics, such as effectiveness, inclusivity, engagement, and alignment with educational standards and goals.

4.5.2 Quality management in education

Term: *quality management in education* (*quality management*)

Definition: Management about quality in education.

NOTE: Quality management in education can include establishing quality policies, educational objectives, and processes to achieve these objectives through quality planning, quality assurance, quality control, and continuous quality improvement in teaching, learning, and institutional practices.

4.5.3 Quality assurance

Term: *quality assurance* (*quality assurance*)

Definition: Part of *quality management in education* focused on providing confidence that quality requirements will be fulfilled.

4.5.4 Quality control

Term: *quality control* (*quality control*)

Definition: Part of *quality management in education* focused on fulfilling quality requirements.

4.5.5 Risk

Term: *risk* (*risk*)

Definition: Combination of the probability of an event and its consequences.

4.5.6 Unintended event

Term: *unintended event* (*unintended event*)

Definition: Event that is not part of the normal course of a *process* but might influence it

NOTE 1: An unintended event can be either expected or unexpected.

NOTE 2: Activities in a process are deliberate and have a purpose. In an ideal situation, the purposes are always fulfilled. If an activity in whatever other process has an impact on the process currently analysed, the effect of this activity is perceived by the current process as an unintended event. Then, the course of the process may deviate from the expected one. Such an exception from the desired course might prove negative or positive compared to the desired process outcome.

4.6 Process management

4.6.1 Process

Term: *process* (*process*)

Definition: Set of interrelated or interacting activities that use inputs to deliver an intended result.

NOTE 1: Whether the “intended result” of a process is called output, product, or service depends on the context of the reference.

NOTE 2: Inputs to a process are generally the outputs of other processes, and outputs of a process are generally the inputs to other processes.

NOTE 3: Two or more interrelated and interacting processes in a series can also be referred to as a process.

4.6.2 Process model

Term: *process model* (*process model*)

Definition: Representation of a *process*.

4.6.3 Product

Term: *product* (*product*)

Definition: Output of an organization that can be produced without any transaction taking place between the organization and the customer.

NOTE 1: Production of a product is achieved without any transaction necessarily taking place between provider and customer, but can often involve this service element upon its delivery to the customer.

NOTE 2: Hardware is tangible, and its amount is a countable characteristic (e.g. tyres). Processed materials are tangible, and their amount is continuous (e.g., fuel and soft drinks). Hardware and processed materials are often referred to as goods. The software consists of information regardless of delivery medium (e.g. computer program, mobile phone app, instruction manual, dictionary content, musical composition copyright, driver's license).

4.6.4 Service

Term: *service* (*service*)

Definition: Output of an *organization* with at least one activity necessarily performed between the organization and the customer.

NOTE 1: The dominant elements of a service are generally intangible.

NOTE 2: Service often involves activities at the interface with the customer to establish customer requirements and upon service delivery and can involve a continuing relationship such as banks, accountants or public organizations, e.g. schools.

4.6.5 Output

Term: *output* (*output*)

Definition: Result of a *process*.

NOTE: Whether an output of the *organization* is a *product* or a *service* depends on the preponderance of the characteristics involved, e.g. a painting for sale in a gallery is a product. In contrast, the supply of a commissioned painting is a service; a hamburger bought in a retail store is a product, whereas receiving an order and serving a hamburger ordered in a restaurant is part of a service.

4.7 Time

4.7.1 Appointment

Term: *appointment* (*appointment*)

Definition: Arrangement to meet someone at a particular time and place.

4.8 Responsibility

4.8.1 Commitment

Term: *commitment* (*commitment*)

Definition: Action resulting in an obligation by one or more of the participants in the act to comply with a rule or perform a contract.

4.9 Information management

4.9.1 Data

Term: *data* (*data*)

Definition: Re-interpretable representation of information in a formalized manner suitable for communication, interpretation or processing.

NOTE: Data can be processed by humans or automatically.

4.9.2 Data repository

Term: *data repository (data repository)*

Definition: An identifiable *data* storage facility.

4.9.3 Educational data

Term: *educational data (healthcare data)*

Definition: Any *data* produced during educational activities.

4.9.4 Educational information

Term: *educational information (healthcare information)*

Definition: An *information* about a *person*, relevant to his or her *education*.

4.9.5 Information

Term: *information (information)*

Definition: Knowledge concerning objects that within a certain context has a particular meaning.

NOTE 1: Facts, events, things, processes, and ideas, including concepts, are examples of objects.

NOTE 2: Information is meaningful. Data might be regarded as information once its meaning is revealed [5].

4.9.6 Information model

Term: *information model (information model)*

Definition: Formal model of a bounded set of facts, concepts or instructions to meet a specified requirement [6].

4.9.7 Electronic educational record

Term: *electronic educational record (electronic health record)*

Definition: A repository of *information* regarding the education of a learner refers to a collection of data and *information* about a student's academic progress, personal development, and educational history, stored in a computer-able format. This repository contains grades, attendance, learning assessments, and other relevant educational data that can be used for tracking, analysis, and decision-making to support the learner's educational journey (adopted from the Electronic Health Record definition [7]).

4.9.8 Medium

Term: *medium* (*medium*)

Definition: Material on which data is stored (e.g. a magnetic disk) [8].

4.10 Symbols and abbreviations

5 Concepts related to educational stakeholders

Educational stakeholders are the various roles played by individuals (natural persons) and organisations (legal entities) within the educational domain.

5.1 General

A model showing the associations between concepts related to actors in education is shown in Figures 2 and 3. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 2: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to educational actors (i)

Figure 3: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to educational actors (ii)

5.2 Educational actor

Term: *educational actor* (*healthcare actor*)

Definition: The role of an organization or person in *education*

NOTE 1: The involvement of the *educational actor* will be either direct (for example, the actual provision of *education*), or indirect (for example, at organizational level)

NOTE 2: According to this definition, people or organizations responsible for the funding, payment, or reimbursement of *education* provision are *education* actors, as well as organizations responsible for *education* delivery

NOTE 3: We follow the ISO 21001 definition for educational stakeholders.

EXAMPLE: The role of teacher, the role of university

Table 1 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 4.

Table 1: Associations of *educational actor* (tab:01)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>role</i>		<i>educator</i>	
		<i>learner</i>	
		<i>educational personnel</i>	
		<i>educational third party</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	participates in	1..* <i>education</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	identifies or states	0..* <i>educational matter</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	defines	0..* <i>educational thread</i>
0..*	<i>educational actor</i>	makes decisions assisted by	0..* <i>educational guideline</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	applies	0..* <i>learning plan</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	is responsible for	0..* <i>sharable educational data repository</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	expresses	0..* <i>demand for education</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	sends out	0..* <i>educational information request</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	receives	0..* <i>educational information request</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	sends out	0..* <i>educational report</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	receives	0..* <i>educational report</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	performs	0..* <i>educational activity element</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	is responsible for	0..* <i>automated education</i>
0..*	<i>educational actor</i>	provides	0..* <i>educational funds</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	has observed	0..* <i>observed educational condition</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	describes	0..* <i>potential educational condition</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	assigns	0..* <i>educational mandate</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	is assigned to	1 <i>educational actor</i>
0..1	<i>person</i>	can have role of	0..* <i>educational actor</i>
0..1	<i>organization</i>	can have role of	0..* <i>educational actor</i>
0..*	<i>certificate related to an educational matter</i>	is issued by	1..* <i>educational actor</i>

Figure 4: Educational actor (UML representation)

5.3 Learner

Term: *learner* (subject of care)

Synonyms: student, pupil

Definition: A *person role* of someone who seeks to receive, is receiving, or has received *education*

EXAMPLE: A role of student enrolled in a school; a role of trainee participating in a vocational training program

Table 2 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 5.

Table 2: Associations of *learner* (tab:02)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational actor</i>			
<i>person role</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>learner</i>	seeks to receive, is receiving, or has received	1..* <i>education</i>
1	<i>learner</i>	has	1..* <i>educational state</i>
1	<i>learner</i>	has or has had	0..* <i>educational need</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	maintains	0..* <i>personal educational record</i>
1	<i>learner</i>	performs	0..* <i>self-learning activity</i>
1	<i>learner</i>	has	0..* <i>guardian</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	has	0..* <i>consent competence</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	expresses	0..1 <i>learner desire</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	gives	0..* <i>informed consent</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	states	0..* <i>dissent</i>
1	<i>learner</i>	participates in	0..* <i>educational contact</i>
0..*	<i>learner proxy</i>	has the right to take decisions on behalf of	1 <i>learner</i>
0..*	<i>learner preference delay</i>	is caused by	1 <i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational process</i>	is performed for	1 <i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	is performed for	1 <i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational matter</i>	concerns	1 <i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	concerns	1 <i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational record</i>	concerns	1 <i>learner</i>
0..*	<i>educational third party</i>	supports	1..* <i>learner</i>
0..*	<i>reason for demand for education</i>	is expressed by	0..1 <i>learner</i>

Figure 5: Learner (UML representation)

5.4 Guardian

Term: *guardian* (next of kin)

Definition: *person role* being either the closest living relative of the *learner* or identified as the one he has a close relationship with

NOTE 1: The person that is the *guardian* may participate implicitly or explicitly in *education* by sometimes being a *learner proxy* when the *learner* has impaired consent competence. Thereby in these circumstances a person that is next of kin can perform the role of a *educational third party*.

NOTE 2: A person may play the role of *guardian* to more than one *learner*

EXAMPLE: When enrolling in an educational institution, a student designates their next of kin as an emergency contact. If the student experiences an accident or requires urgent communication, the

administration contacts the designated relative.

Table 3 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 6.

Table 3: Associations of *guardian* (tab:03)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>person role</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1	<i>learner</i>	has	0..1 <i>guardian</i>

Figure 6: Guardian (UML representation)

5.5 Educator

Term: *educator* (*healthcare provider*)

Synonyms: Education provider, learning provider, educational service provider, learning service provider

Definition: *educational actor* that is able to be assigned one or more *educational period mandates*

NOTE 1: The personnel of a *educational organization* that is a *educator* may include both *education professionals* and others which participate in the provision of *education*

NOTE 2: This International Standard includes only two specialization of *educator*. This is not meant to exclude the possibility of other specializations. The necessary specialisations may be added in jurisdictions where other kinds of *educational actors* are included in the concept of *educator*.

NOTE 3: According to this definition, organizations solely responsible for the funding, payment, or reimbursement of *education* provision are not *educator*; for this International Standard, they are considered as *education* third parties.

EXAMPLE: A university, college, or language school offering educational programmes and courses is an education provider. These institutions develop educational programmes, organise the learning process, and

assess students' academic performance.

Table 4 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 7.

Table 4: Associations of *educator* (tab:04)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational actor</i>		<i>educational organization</i>	
		<i>education professional</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educator</i>	provides	1..* <i>education</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	has care period mandate for	1..* <i>mandated period of education</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	is responsible for	1..* <i>mandated period of education</i>
1..*	<i>educator</i>	performs	1..* <i>education provider activity</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	receives	1..* <i>demand for education</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	accepts or denies	1..* <i>demand for education</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	is responsible for	0..* <i>professional educational record</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	manages	0..* <i>episode of learning support</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	is able to be assigned	1..* <i>educational period mandate</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	arranges	0..* <i>educational initial contact</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	states	1..* <i>educational commitment</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	has	1 <i>educational activity directory</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	is responsible for	0..* <i>resource delay</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	performs	0..* <i>educational resource management</i>

Figure 7: Educator (UML representation)

5.6 Educational organization

Term: *educational organization* (*healthcare organization*)

Synonyms: education organization, educational delivery organization

Definition: *educator* being an *organization role*

NOTE 1: The personnel of a *educational organization* that is a *educator* may include both *education* professionals and others which participate in the provision of *education*.

NOTE 2: Groupings or subdivisions of an organization, such as departments or sub-departments, may also be considered as organizations where there is a need to identify them. The internal structure of an organization is described by its organizational pattern. Therefore, an organization may be considered a stand-alone or superstructure containing departments and sub-departments, such as other lower-level organizations. A *educational organization* represents any such organisation's role when it is involved in directly provision of *education* activities.

NOTE 3: Effectively, a *educational organization* relies on the activity performed by *education* personnel, whether employed, contracting, or with temporary informal though functional relationships between them. A *education* team working together, for example, a specific type of clinical process with participants from different departments, is also a kind of *educational organization*.

NOTE 4: A free-standing self-employed solo practising *education* professional shall be considered as the only

member of his/her own *educational organization*.

NOTE 5: Organizations may have several different roles. When an organization acts in a role where its *education* personnel participate in the direct provision of *education*, it is called a *educational organization*.

EXAMPLE: School, university, college, university or college departments, a company providing internship

Table 5 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 8.

Table 5: Associations of *educational organization* (tab:05)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educator</i>			
Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>educational personnel</i>
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational organization</i>	0..*	<i>educational personnel</i>
1..*	<i>educational organization</i>	0..*	<i>core learning plan</i>
1	<i>educational organization</i>	1..*	<i>educational quality management</i>

Figure 8: Educational organization (UML representation)

5.7 Educational employment

Term: *educational employment* (*healthcare employment*)

Definition: Contractual framework between an *education* personnel and an *education* organization describing the roles and responsibilities assigned to that *education* personnel

EXAMPLE:School teacher, university lecturer, educational consultant, teaching assistant

Table 6 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 9.

Table 6: Associations of *educational employment* (tab:06)

Association concept					
Association concept		Links			
1	<i>educational employment</i>	1	<i>educational personnel</i>	1	<i>educational organization</i>

Figure 9: Educational employment (UML representation)

5.8 Educational personnel

Term: *educational personnel* (*healthcare personnel*)

Definition: Individual *educational actor* being a *person role* in an *educational organization*

EXAMPLE:Teacher, professor, tutor, counsellor, librarian, teaching assistant, principal, school nurse, department head, educational consultant, etc.

Table 7 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 10.

Table 7: Associations of *educational personnel* (tab:07)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational actor</i>		<i>education professional</i>	
<i>person role</i>			
<i>educational resource</i>			
Component of		Aggregation of	
1	<i>educational organization</i>		
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational organization</i>	appoints	0..* <i>educational personnel</i>
1..*	<i>educational personnel</i>	participates in	0..* <i>educational contact</i>

Figure 10: Educational personnel (UML representation)

5.9 Education professional

Term: *education professional (healthcare professional)*

Definition: *educational personnel* having a *education professional* entitlement recognized in a given jurisdiction

NOTE: The *education professional* entitlement entitles a *education professional* to provide *education* independent of a role in a *educational organization*.

EXAMPLE: Teacher, professor, tutor, educational consultant, counsellor, librarian, etc.

Table 8 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 11.

Table 8: Associations of *education professional* (tab:08)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educator</i>			
<i>educational personnel</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>education professional</i>	has	1..* <i>educational professional entitlement</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	issues	0..* <i>referral</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	issues	0..* <i>request</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	manages	0..* <i>educational activity period</i>
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	maintains	0..* <i>professional educational record</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	has ratified	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
0..*	<i>education professional</i>	manages	0..* <i>demand for education</i>
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	identifies	0..* <i>prognostic educational condition</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	has determined	0..* <i>working educational conclusion</i>
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	has ruled out	0..* <i>excluded educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>professionally assessed condition</i>	is identified by	1 <i>education professional</i>
0..*	<i>prescribed self-learning</i>	is prescribed by	1 <i>education professional</i>
0..*	<i>prescribed third party activity</i>	is prescribed by	1 <i>education professional</i>
1..*	<i>educational personnel</i>	performs	0..* <i>educational needs assessment</i>

Figure 11: Educational professional (UML representation)

5.10 Educational professional entitlement

Term: *educational professional entitlement (healthcare professional entitlement)*

Synonyms: teaching or teacher accreditation or certification, professional registration

Definition: Registered authorization given to a *person* in order to allow the *person* to have or perform specific roles in *education*

NOTE 1: Entitlement is usually backed by evidence of receiving or continuously receiving the necessary qualification, relevant education and training.

NOTE 2: The official entitlement of an educational professional forms the foundation for his/her official duties and rights.

EXAMPLE: Diploma, teaching certification, professional registration (e.g. certified teacher).

Table 9 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 12.

Table 9: Associations of *educational professional entitlement* (tab:09)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1	<i>education professional</i>	has	1..*	<i>educational professional entitlement</i>

Figure 12: Educational professional entitlement (UML representation)

5.11 Educational third party

Term: *educational third party* (*healthcare third party*)

Definition: *educational actor* other than a *educator* or the *learner*

NOTE 1: According to this definition, a relative (family member) aiding the *learner*, any actor responsible for social support, or the funding, payment, or reimbursement of *education* are *educational third parties*.

NOTE 2: *educational third party* is an abstract superordinate generic concept which is only fully supported through the use of one of its subordinate specific concepts

EXAMPLE: Tutoring services (a private tutor – hired to provide one-on-one support tailored to the student’s learning needs), educational technology providers, online course providers

Table 10 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 13.

Table 10: Associations of *educational third party* (tab:10)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>educational actor</i>		<i>other educator</i>		
		<i>learner proxy</i>		
		<i>Educational Supporting Organization</i>		
Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational third party</i>	supports	1..*	<i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational third party</i>	performs	1..*	<i>educational third party activity</i>

Figure 13: Educational third party (UML representation)

5.12 Other educator

Term: *other educator* (*other carer*)

Synonyms: informal educator

Definition: *educational third party* being a *person role*

EXAMPLE: A relative (family member), private tutor

Table 11 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 14.

Table 11: Associations of *other educator* (tab:11)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational third party</i>	
<i>person role</i>	

Figure 14: Other educator (UML representation)

5.13 Educational supporting organization

Term: *Educational Supporting Organization (healthcare supporting organization)*

Synonyms: *education* supporting organization

Definition: *educational third party* being an organizational role

EXAMPLE: Educational aid organization, a tutoring service organization, the operator of an online learning platform, family.

Table 12 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 15.

Table 12: Associations of *Educational Supporting Organization* (tab:12)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational third party</i>	
<i>organization role</i>	

Figure 15: Educational supporting organization (UML representation)

5.14 Learner proxy

Term: *learner proxy* (*subject of care proxy*)

Synonyms: *learner* agent

Definition: *educational third party* being a person role with the right to take decisions on behalf of the *learner*

NOTE: In *ISO 21001 learner* agent is the preferred term for this concept

EXAMPLE: Academic advisors – sometimes, academic advisors may serve as proxies when a learner is not able to handle certain aspects of their academic progression, such as signing up for courses or resolving academic issues. Special education assistants – these professionals act as proxies for students with special needs, ensuring their educational needs are met and advocating on their behalf in terms of accommodations or adjustments.

Table 13 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 16.

Table 13: Associations of *learner proxy* (tab:13)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>person role</i>			
<i>educational third party</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..1	<i>learner proxy</i>	gives	0..* <i>informed consent</i>
0..*	<i>learner proxy</i>	has the right to take decisions on behalf of	1 <i>learner</i>
0..1	<i>learner proxy</i>	states	0..* <i>dissent</i>
0..*	<i>learner proxy</i>	has	1 <i>consent competence</i>
0..*	<i>reason for demand for education</i>	is expressed by	0..* <i>learner proxy</i>
0..*	<i>learner proxy</i>	maintains	0..* <i>personal educational record</i>
0..1	<i>learner proxy</i>	expresses	0..* <i>learner desire</i>

Figure 16: Learner proxy (UML representation)

6 Concepts related to education matters

6.1 General

A model showing the associations between concepts related to education matters and the other concepts defined in this International Standard is shown in Figures 17 and 18. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 17: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to educational matters (i)

Figure 18: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to educational matters (ii)

6.2 Educational matter

Term: *educational matter* (*healthcare matter*)

Definition: Representation of a matter related to the education of a *learner* and/or the provision of *education* to that *learner*, as identified by one or more *educational actors*.

NOTE 1: *educational matter* is a very broad and flexible concept that includes anything related to the education or the educational development of a student. This means that *education conditions*, *educational activities*, *educational problems*, the results of *educational activities*, etc. all can be identified as *educational matters*. Therefore, *educational matter* might have several specializations and associations.

NOTE 2: According to this definition, an *educational matter* can represent a subject, a topic, or another kind of *education condition*. In addition, an *educational matter* may represent, for example, a request for an activity (instructional or evaluative) by the *learner* or another *educational actor*.

Table 14 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 19. EXAMPLE:Examinations and assessments – activities involving the evaluation of a student’s knowledge, skills, or understanding, such as standardized tests, quizzes, assignments, and final exams. Educational funding – issues related to scholarships, grants, student loans, or government funding aimed at supporting the costs of education.

Table 14 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 19.

Table 14: Associations of *educational matter* (tab:14)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
		<i>education issue</i>		
Association from		Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational matter</i>	concerns	1	<i>learner</i>
0..1	<i>educational matter</i>	is used as label for	0..*	<i>educational record component</i>
0..1	<i>educational matter</i>	is used as label for	0..*	<i>educational record extract</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	identifies or states	0..*	<i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>demand mandate</i>	has topic	1..*	<i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>educational period mandate</i>	has topic	1..*	<i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>demand for education</i>	concerns	1..*	<i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>mandate to export personal information</i>	has topic	1..*	<i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>educational thread</i>	links	0..*	<i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>certificate related to an educational matter</i>	attests	1..*	<i>educational matter</i>

Figure 19: Educational matter (UML representation)

6.3 Education issue

Term: *education issue* (*health issue*)

Definition: Representation of an issue related to the education of a *learner* as identified by one or more *educational actors*

NOTE: According to this definition, an *education issue* can correspond to a learning problem, a subject matter difficulty, an educational challenge, or another kind of *education condition*.

EXAMPLE: Quality of education – concerns about the effectiveness of teaching methods, curriculum quality, and learning objective.

Table 15 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 20.

Table 15: Associations of *education issue* (tab:15)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational matter</i>		<i>education condition</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>education issue</i>	determines	0..* <i>educational activity period element</i>
0..*	<i>learning process</i>	addresses	1..* <i>education issue</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	addresses	1..* <i>education issue</i>
0..*	<i>episode of learning support</i>	is centred on	1 <i>education issue</i>
0..*	<i>education provider activity</i>	addresses	1..* <i>education issue</i>
0..*	<i>educational guideline</i>	is centred on	1..* <i>education issue</i>

Figure 20: Educational issue (UML representation)

6.4 Education condition

Term: *education condition* (*health condition*)

Definition: Observed or potential observable aspects of the *educational state* at a given time

NOTE 1: In the perspective of education, the term *education conditions* is often used to label a challenging or adverse condition (learning difficulties, behavioural issues, etc.) because it may motivate certain *educational activities*.

NOTE 2: An *educational state* is an object, a perception of which is an education condition. The underlying *educational state* is nevertheless present even if not perceived by an observer, for example, a *learner* having a learning difficulty before a teacher identifies it.

NOTE 3: In an *learning process*, the *educational state* of the *learner* is process input and also the process

output. The evolving *educational state* follows a life cycle and along its successive steps, is observed as different *education conditions*: initial, *observed educational condition*, *considered educational condition*, *professionally assessed condition*, *resultant educational condition* (the outcome of the process), evaluated.

EXAMPLE: Academic performance – the level of a student’s success in meeting the expected learning objective, including grades, test scores, and overall achievement.

Table 16 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 21.

Table 16: Associations of *education condition* (tab:16)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education issue</i>		<i>observed educational condition</i>	
		<i>potential educational condition</i>	
		<i>educational problem</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>education condition</i>	governs the choice of	0..* <i>educational pathway</i>
0..*	<i>educational condition evolution</i>	shows the evolution of	1..* <i>education condition</i>
0..*	<i>educational pathway</i>	addresses	1..* <i>education condition</i>

Figure 21: Educational condition (UML representation)

6.5 Observed educational condition

Term: *observed educational condition* (*observed condition*)

Definition: *education condition* observed by a *educational actor*

NOTE 1: *education professionals* and *learners* are examples of *educational actors* that can perceive the observed aspect of a *educational state*.

NOTE 2: An *observed educational condition* is a *education issue* and as such is a representation of aspect(s) of the *educational state*.

EXAMPLE: A student is frequently disengaged, struggles to complete assignments on time, and performs poorly on assessment. The teacher observes an educational condition—possible learning difficulties or lack of motivation.

Table 17 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 22.

Table 17: Associations of *observed educational condition* (tab:17)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education condition</i>		<i>professionally assessed condition</i>	
		<i>resultant educational condition</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational state</i>	is observed as	0..* <i>observed educational condition</i>
1	<i>observed educational condition</i>	has been observed during	1 <i>educational condition period</i>
0..*	<i>considered educational condition</i>	is based on	1..* <i>observed educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>educational investigation</i>	reveals	0..* <i>observed educational condition</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	has observed	0..* <i>observed educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>working educational conclusion</i>	is consistent with	1..* <i>observed educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>excluded educational condition</i>	is not consistent with	1..* <i>observed educational condition</i>

Figure 22: Observed educational condition (UML representation)

6.6 Professionally assessed condition

Term: *professionally assessed condition* (*professionally assessed condition*)

Definition: *observed educational condition* assessed by a *education professional* concerning the origin, the course, the difficulty or the impact of the *educational state*

EXAMPLE: A university professor notices that the student struggles with reading comprehension and written assignments, despite putting in significant effort. The professor refers the student to the university's educational psychologist for further assessment.

Table 18 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 23.

Table 18: Associations of *professionally assessed condition* (tab:18)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>observed educational condition</i>		<i>working educational conclusion</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>prognostic educational condition</i>	is based on	1..* <i>professionally assessed condition</i>
0..*	<i>professionally assessed condition</i>	is identified by	1 <i>education professional</i>

Figure 23: Professionally assessed condition (UML representation)

6.7 Resultant educational condition

Term: *resultant educational condition* (*resultant condition*)

Definition: *observed educational condition* representing an *output educational state*

NOTE: A *resultant educational condition* can represent the output *educational state* after a single *educational activity* element, a bundle of *educational investigations* and/or *educational instructions* in a *educational process* and also the outcome after a complete *learning process*.

EXAMPLE: A group of medical students participates in a clinical simulation designed to improve emergency response skills. After completing the training, their performance is assessed to determine the resultant educational condition—the educational state achieved after the learning process.

Table 19 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 24.

Table 19: Associations of *resultant educational condition* (tab:19)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>observed educational condition</i>				
Association from		Association name	Association to	
1	<i>output educational state</i>	is observed as	0..*	<i>resultant educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>resultant educational condition</i>	Is input to	0..*	<i>educational process outcome evaluation</i>

Figure 24: Resultant educational condition (UML representation)

6.8 Potential educational condition

Term: *potential educational condition* (*potential health condition*)

Definition: Possible future or current *education condition* described by a *educational actor*

NOTE: A *potential educational condition* is not yet observed but represents an imagined, possible observation of aspects of a current or future educational state.

EXAMPLE: Teacher analyzes students participation in the course and missed assignment deadlines. Although these students haven't failed yet, the teacher predicts they may struggle later in the course.

Table 20 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 25.

Table 20: Associations of *potential educational condition* (tab:20)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education condition</i>		<i>prognostic educational condition</i>	
		<i>target educational condition</i>	
		<i>risk educational condition</i>	
		<i>considered educational condition</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	describes	0..* <i>potential educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>potential educational condition</i>	represents potential aspects of	1 <i>educational state</i>

Figure 25: Potential educational condition (UML representation)

6.9 Considered educational condition

Term: *considered educational condition* (*considered condition*)

Definition: *potential educational condition* considered by a *educational actor* on the basis of one or more *observed educational conditions*

NOTE 1: A request for care normally includes a *education condition* or indicator observed by the *learner* and also a question about what the reason for that indicator might be. It is the *potential educational condition* in this question (the *education condition* behind the indicator) that is called a *considered educational condition*.

NOTE 2: A *considered educational condition* remains considered until the associated *observed educational conditions* are changed or completed. *educational investigation* and/or *educational instruction* result in new observations that can verify or not verify the (suspected) *considered educational condition*. When a *considered educational condition* is verified, it is transformed into an *observed educational condition* and/or *professionally assessed condition* that also could be labelled as a *working educational conclusion*. If a *considered educational condition* cannot be verified by relevant *educational activities*, it is transformed into an *excluded educational condition*.

EXAMPLE: A teacher notices that a student struggles with reading fluency and comprehension. He frequently misreads words, skips lines, and has difficulty understanding text. Based on these observations, the teacher considers a potential educational condition—dyslexia—but has not yet confirmed it.

Table 21 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 26.

Table 21: Associations of *considered educational condition* (tab:21)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>potential educational condition</i>		<i>working educational conclusion</i>	
		<i>excluded educational condition</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>considered educational condition</i>	is based on	1..* <i>observed educational condition</i>

Figure 26: Considered educational condition (UML representation)

6.10 Working educational conclusion

Term: *working educational conclusion* (*working diagnosis*)

Definition: *considered educational condition* that one or more *education professionals* have determined to be the most consistent with the currently known *observed educational conditions*

NOTE 1: A *working educational conclusion* is used as a label for the *considered educational condition* that one or more *education professionals* assess as the most probable *education condition* and that could be concluded after further observations. The basis for such assessments is the already *observed educational conditions*.

NOTE 2: Different *education professionals* may make different interpretations and assessments of the *observed educational conditions* and thereby come to different conclusions and different *working educational conclusion*.

EXAMPLE: The student is struggling with her coursework, particularly in reading-intensive subjects. She frequently misinterprets written instructions, takes longer to process texts, and has trouble summarizing key concepts.

Table 22 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 27.

Table 22: Associations of *working educational conclusion* (tab:22)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>professionally assessed condition</i>			
<i>considered educational condition</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	has determined	0..* <i>working educational conclusion</i>
0..*	<i>working educational conclusion</i>	is consistent with	1..* <i>observed educational condition</i>

Figure 27: Working educational conclusion (UML representation)

6.11 Excluded educational condition

Term: *excluded educational condition* (*excluded condition*)

Synonyms: discounted educational condition, non-verified educational condition, ruled out educational condition, ruled out considered educational condition

Definition: *considered educational condition* that one or more *education professionals* have determined not to be consistent with the known *observed educational conditions*

EXAMPLE:The student is struggling with her coursework. She finds it difficult to complete assignments on time, performs poorly on exams, and often fails to recall key concepts during discussions. Concerned about her academic performance, she consults the university’s academic support center.

Table 23 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 28.

Table 23: Associations of *excluded educational condition* (tab:23)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>considered educational condition</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	has ruled out	0..* <i>excluded educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>excluded educational condition</i>	is not consistent with	1..* <i>observed educational condition</i>

Figure 28: Excluded educational condition (UML representation)

6.12 Target educational condition

Term: *target educational condition (target condition)*

Synonyms: target learning condition, intended learning outcome

Definition: *potential educational condition* representing *learning objectives* and/or *educational goals*

NOTE: Assessment of needs for *educational activities* includes identification of *learning objectives* and/or *educational goals*. These inform decisions about relevant activities to create or update the *learning plan*.

EXAMPLE: The target educational condition for a student who is struggling with reading comprehension is to achieve grade-level proficiency in reading in the shortest time period.

Table 24 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 29.

Table 24: Associations of *target educational condition* (tab:24)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>potential educational condition</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>target educational condition</i>	represents	0..* <i>learning objective</i>
1..*	<i>target educational condition</i>	is input to	0..* <i>educational process outcome evaluation</i>
0..*	<i>target educational condition</i>	represents	0..* <i>educational goal</i>

Figure 29: Target educational condition (UML representation)

6.13 Prognostic educational condition

Term: *prognostic educational condition* (*prognostic condition*)

Synonyms: prognostic learning condition

Definition: *potential educational condition* representing the expected course of a *educational state* as assessed by *education professionals*

EXAMPLE: A first-year university student is performing poorly in his introductory mathematics and science courses. His professors notice that he struggles with foundational concepts and has difficulty keeping up with coursework. Concerned about his future academic success the student meets with an academic advisor and learning specialist for evaluation.

Table 25 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 30.

Table 25: Associations of *prognostic educational condition* (tab:25)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>potential educational condition</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>prognostic educational condition</i>	is based on	1..* <i>professionally assessed condition</i>
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	identifies	0..* <i>prognostic educational condition</i>

Figure 30: Prognostic educational condition (UML representation)

6.14 Risk educational condition

Term: *risk educational condition* (*risk condition*)

Synonyms: risk learning condition

Definition: *potential educational condition* representing an unintended future *educational state*

NOTE: Risk is defined as the combination of the probability of an event and its consequences, but a *risk educational condition* focuses solely on the possible negative consequences for the educational process or outcome.

EXAMPLE: In the context of education, a risk educational condition might refer to a situation where a student is at risk of not achieving certain educational goals due to various factors. For example, if a student has significant gaps in knowledge that could lead to future academic failure, this can be considered a risk educational condition.

Table 26 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 31.

Table 26: Associations of *risk educational condition* (tab:26)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>potential educational condition</i>	

Figure 31: Risk educational condition (UML representation)

6.15 Educational problem

Term: *educational problem* (*health problem*)

Definition: *education condition* considered by a *educational actor* to be a problem

NOTE: *educational problems* can be single observations but are usually more compound as a summary of several observations. Single observations are often criteria for the more compound health condition considered to be a *educational problem*.

EXAMPLE: Behavioural issues, risk of school dropout.

Table 27 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 32.

Table 27: Associations of *educational problem* (tab:27)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>education condition</i>	

Figure 32: Educational problem (UML representation)

6.16 Educational state

Term: *educational state* (*health state*)

Definition: Cognitive and emotional functions, personal factors, learning activities, participation, and environmental aspects as the composite education of a *learner*

NOTE: An observation of an *educational state* is an *education condition*. An *educational state* may give rise to more than one observation, resulting in more than one *education condition*. The underlying *educational state* is nevertheless present even if not perceived by an observer.

EXAMPLE: A student having a learning difficulty before it is identified by a teacher.

Table 28 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 33.

Table 28: Associations of *educational state* (tab:28)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>input educational state</i>	
		<i>output educational state</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>learner</i>	has	1..* <i>educational state</i>
1	<i>educational state</i>	is observed as	0..* <i>observed educational condition</i>
0..*	<i>potential educational condition</i>	represents potential aspects of	1 <i>educational state</i>
0..*	<i>educational instruction</i>	influences	1 <i>educational state</i>
0..*	<i>educational need</i>	is deficit in	1 <i>educational state</i>
0..*	<i>educational investigation</i>	clarifies	1 <i>educational state</i>

Figure 33: Educational state (UML representation)

6.17 Input educational state

Term: *input educational state* (*input health state*)

Definition: *educational state* at the initiation of an *educational process*

NOTE: The *output educational state* from one *educational process* may be the *input educational state* for a subsequent *educational process*.

EXAMPLE: Student's input educational state includes general academic abilities, study habits, and readiness to engage with the course content. As she progresses through her studies, the educational state she enters after each course could serve as the input educational state for her next course or academic year, reflecting any changes in her knowledge, skills, or learning habits.

Table 29 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 34.

Table 29: Associations of *input educational state* (tab:29)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational state</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..1	<i>educational condition evolution</i>	relates to	1 <i>input educational state</i>
0..1	<i>input educational state</i>	is input to	1 <i>educational process</i>

Figure 34: Input educational state (UML representation)

6.18 Output educational state

Term: *output educational state* (*output health state*)

Synonyms: outcome

Definition: *educational state* when an *educational process* ends

EXAMPLE: At the end of the first semester, a university student completes his introductory economics course. His output educational state is characterized by his acquired knowledge of key economic principles, improved critical thinking skills, and his ability to apply economic concepts to real-world situations. This output educational state reflects the academic progress the student has made throughout the course and serves as a basis for his readiness to move on to more advanced courses in the subsequent semester.

Table 30 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 35.

Table 30: Associations of *output educational state* (tab:30)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational state</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational process</i>	has output	0..1 <i>output educational state</i>
1	<i>output educational state</i>	is observed as	0..* <i>resultant educational condition</i>

Figure 35: Output educational state (UML representation)

6.19 Educational need

Term: *educational need* (*health need*)

Definition: Deficit in the current *educational state* compared to aspects of a desired future *educational state*

NOTE 1: An *educational need* is the deficit in a student's educational state.

NOTE 2: The current *educational state* is observed as *observed educational conditions*.

NOTE 3: The desired future *educational state* can be a *learning objective* expressed as *target educational conditions*.

NOTE 4: The *educational need* can be identified and formulated by the *learner* or by any other *educational actor*.

EXAMPLE: A university student is struggling with time management and organizational skills, which is affecting her ability to complete assignments on time. Her current educational state shows a deficit in these areas compared to the desired future educational state where she would efficiently manage her time, meet deadlines, and improve her academic performance. The student's educational need is identified as the need for better organizational and time management skills. She may address this need by seeking help from a university tutor, attending workshops, or using organizational tools to enhance her skills.

Table 31 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 36.

Table 31: Associations of *educational need* (tab:31)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1	<i>learner</i>	has or has had	0..*	<i>educational need</i>
0..*	<i>educational need</i>	is background for	0..*	<i>reason for demand for education</i>
1	<i>educational need</i>	is considered during	0..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>
0..*	<i>educational need</i>	is deficit in	1	<i>educational state</i>
1..*	<i>needed educational activity</i>	addresses	1..*	<i>educational need</i>
0..*	<i>learning objective</i>	addresses	1..*	<i>educational need</i>

Figure 36: Educational need (UML representation)

6.20 Educational thread

Term: *educational thread* (*health thread*)

Definition: Defined association between *educational matters* as determined by one or more *educational actors*

NOTE 1: A *educational thread* reconciles a range of *educational matters* reflecting the variety of scopes of *educational actors*, particularly of *educators*.

NOTE 2: A *educational thread* inherently associates the *educational processes* as well as the *educational activity period elements* referring to those *educational matters*.

NOTE 3: A *educational thread* may be established by a team (e.g. a coordination committee).

NOTE 4: A *educational thread* can be built step-by-step, by allowing each *education professional* to add their perspective into a common *educational thread*.

EXAMPLE: A university coordination committee is tasked with developing a comprehensive support plan for students with disabilities. The committee creates an educational thread that connects various educational matters, including the students' learning needs, available resources, accommodations, and teaching strategies. Each educational actor involved, such as lecturers, tutors, disability support staff, and counsellors, contributes their perspective to ensure a well-rounded approach. This educational thread reconciles all the relevant matters, facilitating a coordinated and tailored educational experience for students with disabilities, and continues to evolve as each educator adds their input over time.

Table 32 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 37.

Table 32: Associations of *educational thread* (tab:32)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>educational process interest</i>	
		<i>educational condition evolution</i>	
		<i>educational problem list</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational thread</i>	delineates	0..1 <i>episodes of learning support bundle</i>
1	<i>educational thread</i>	delineates	0..1 <i>educational concern</i>
0..*	<i>educational thread</i>	links	0..* <i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>educational thread</i>	links	0..* <i>educational thread</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	defines	0..* <i>educational thread</i>
0..*	<i>continuity facilitator mandate</i>	has topic	0..* <i>educational thread</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	addresses	0..* <i>educational thread</i>

Figure 37: Educational thread (UML representation)

6.21 Educational process interest

Term: *educational process interest* (*clinical process interest*)

Definition: *educational thread* comprising all *educational matters* related to a specific *learning process*

NOTE: An *educational process interest* makes possible for documentation concerning a *learning process* to follow the *learner* across borders of *educators* and organizational units and as such avoid unnecessary duplication of documentation (to create a *educational concern*)

EXAMPLE: A university has a collaborative interdisciplinary project where students from various departments, such as computer science, engineering, and business, work together. Each department's professors contribute to the students' progress, and the educational process interest comprises all educational matters related to this project. This includes the project's goals, learning objectives, student assessments, feedback, and resources needed. By documenting all relevant educational matters within the educational process interest, the university ensures that the student's progress can be tracked across different departments and instructors without duplicating information. This process enables seamless communication and reduces unnecessary repetition in the documentation, improving the overall learning experience.

Table 33 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 38.

Table 33: Associations of *educational process interest* (tab:33)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational thread</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1	<i>learning process</i>	has	0..1 <i>educational process interest</i>

Figure 38: Educational process interest (UML representation)

6.22 Educational problem list

Term: *educational problem list* (*health problem list*)

Synonyms: education concern list

Definition: *educational thread* linking a set of *educational problems*

EXAMPLE: A university creates an educational problem list for a student who is struggling with multiple aspects of their coursework. The list includes issues such as difficulty in time management, poor performance in exams, lack of participation in group projects, and difficulty in understanding certain complex topics in the curriculum. This educational problem list is a comprehensive collection of the student’s challenges, linking them into an educational thread. It helps the student’s academic advisor, tutors, and other educational professionals to address these problems systematically by providing targeted support and interventions, such as offering study skills workshops, additional tutoring, or adjusting project team assignments. The list allows everyone involved in the student’s education to coordinate their efforts and track progress in resolving the identified problems.

Table 34 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 39.

Table 34: Associations of *educational problem list* (tab:34)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational thread</i>	

Figure 39: Educational problem list (UML representation)

6.23 Educational condition evolution

Term: *educational condition evolution* (*health condition evolution*)

Definition: *educational thread* showing the evolution of *education conditions* during a *educational process*, starting with the *education condition* that represents the *input educational state*

EXAMPLE: A university student begins her semester with a specific educational condition where she has limited knowledge in data science, which is her input educational state. Throughout the semester, she attends lectures, participates in workshops, and completes assignments, improving her understanding of the subject. As her knowledge and skills evolve, the educational condition evolves as well. The educational condition evolution for the student is tracked, showing how her educational state changes, starting from her initial limited knowledge and progressing towards a more advanced understanding of data science by the end of the semester. This evolution is documented to reflect her learning journey, highlighting her progress and the educational interventions that contributed to her development.

Table 35 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 40.

Table 35: Associations of *educational condition evolution* (tab:35)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational thread</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..1	<i>educational condition evolution</i>	relates to	1 <i>input educational state</i>
0..*	<i>educational condition evolution</i>	shows the evolution of	1..* <i>education condition</i>

Figure 40: Educational condition evolution (UML representation)

7 Concepts related to activities

7.1 General

A model showing the associations between the concepts related to activity and the other concepts defined in this International Standard is shown in Figures 41 and 42. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 41: ConceptsRelatedToEducationalActivities (i) (UML representation)

EXAMPLE 2: Additional English lessons organised for students experiencing difficulties in mastering the subject, aimed at improving their knowledge and academic performance.

Table 36 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 43.

Table 36: Associations of *educational activity* (tab:36)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
			<i>education provider activity</i>
			<i>educational third party activity</i>
			<i>self-learning activity</i>
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	0..*	<i>educational activity</i>
0..1	<i>educational process</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity element</i>
0..*	<i>educational activity package</i>		
0..1	<i>educational activity</i>		
0..1	<i>adverse educational event management</i>		
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	1	<i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	1..*	<i>educational goal</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	0..*	<i>educational record</i>
0..*	<i>educational record</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	1	<i>educational activity period</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	1..*	<i>educational resource</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	0..*	<i>educational resource management</i>
0..1	<i>educational commitment</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>educational activity management</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	1	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	0..*	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	0..1	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>educational evaluation</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity</i>

Figure 43: Educational activity (UML representation)

7.3 Education provider activity

Term: *education provider activity* (healthcare provider activity)

Definition: *educational activity* performed by a *educator*

NOTE 1: A *education provider activity* can be performed in relation to several *educational activity period* elements of the same *educational activity period*.

NOTE 2: When the *educator* is a *educational organization*, the *educational activities* are performed by the *educational personnel* of that *educational organization*.

EXAMPLE 1: A university professor, is responsible for teaching a course on data science. Throughout the semester, she engages in multiple education provider activities, ensuring students receive structured instruction, guidance, and assessment.

EXAMPLE 2: Lecture delivery, instructional activity, assignment evaluation, assessment activity, curriculum development, supervision of student

Table 37 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 44.

Table 37: Associations of *education provider activity* (tab:37)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>education provider activity</i>	addresses	1..* <i>education issue</i>
0..*	<i>education provider activity</i>	generates	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
1..*	<i>educator</i>	performs	1..* <i>education provider activity</i>
1..*	<i>educational period mandate</i>	authorizes	0..* <i>education provider activity</i>
0..1	<i>demand for education</i>	ask for	1..* <i>education provider activity</i>
0..*	<i>education provider activity</i>	requires	1..* <i>educational activity mandate</i>
1	<i>educational activity directory</i>	includes	1..* <i>education provider activity</i>

Figure 44: Educator activity (UML representation)

7.4 Educational activity directory

Term: *educational activity directory* (*healthcare activity directory*)

Definition: Directory of the *educational activities* offered by a *educator*

NOTE 1: The *educational activity directory* includes those *educational activities* that the *educator's* *educational personnel* can perform, not those that are actually available at the time of *education* delivery. The ability to perform a *educational activity* implies that the *educator* has the necessary resources.

NOTE 2: The *educational activity directory* is related to the management of *educational processes*.

NOTE 3: *educators* may also have a *educational service directory*. This directory includes the services that can be delivered by *educational processes* using the *educational activities* included in the *educational activity*

directory.

EXAMPLE 1: An educational activity directory that lists all the educational activities that its professors and instructors can provide. This directory serves as a reference for academic planning, course scheduling, and student enrollment.

EXAMPLE 2: Core academic courses, lectures, tutorials, field studies, case studies, laboratory and practical training, thesis supervision

Table 38 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 45.

Table 38: Associations of *educational activity directory* (tab:38)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1	<i>educational activity directory</i>	includes	1..*	<i>education provider activity</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	has	1	<i>educational activity directory</i>

Figure 45: Educational activity directory (UML representation)

7.5 Self-learning activity

Term: *self-learning activity* (*self-care activity*)

Definition: *educational activity* performed by the *learner*

NOTE 1: There are two kinds of *self-learning activities* that should be distinguished: a) *prescribed self-learning* that is included in a *learning plan* and the documentation is included in a professional *educational record*; b) Self performed health related activities that are not prescribed.

NOTE 2: In EN 13940–1:2007 health self-care activity was the preferred term for this concept.

EXAMPLE: A student, is preparing for his upcoming exam. As part of his preparation, he engages in various self-learning activities to reinforce his understanding: lecture slides and required readings, exercises, online discussion forum

Table 39 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 46.

Table 39: Associations of *self-learning activity* (tab:39)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity</i>		<i>prescribed self-learning</i>	
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>self-learning activity</i>	generates	0..* <i>non-ratified educational information</i>
1	<i>learner</i>	performs	0..* <i>self-learning activity</i>

Figure 46: Self-learning activity (UML representation)

7.6 Prescribed self-learning

Term: *prescribed self-learning* (*prescribed self-care*)

Definition: *self-learning activity* prescribed by a *education professional*

EXAMPLE:As part of the curriculum, a professor assigns to students specific self-learning activities to reinforce classroom learning and develop practical skills: required readings and reflections. The university’s learning management system provides interactive online modules, completion of these modules is mandatory and graded.

Table 40 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 47.

Table 40: Associations of *prescribed self-learning* (tab:40)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>self-learning activity</i>				
Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>prescribed self-learning</i>	is prescribed by	1	<i>education professional</i>
1..*	<i>prescribed self-learning</i>	take place during	1	<i>self-study period</i>

Figure 47: Prescribed self-learning (UML representation)

7.7 Educational third party activity

Term: *educational third party activity* (*healthcare third party activity*)

Synonyms: healthcare contributing activity

Definition: *educational activity* performed by a *educational third party*

NOTE: There are two kinds of *educational third party activities* that should be distinguished. Prescribed contributing care that is included in a *learning plan* and the documentation is included in a *educational record*. *educational third party activity* that are not prescribed.

EXAMPLE 1: A first-year university student struggling with advanced mathematics. Her mother provides regular tutoring sessions to help her understand complex concepts. Since this support is coming from a non-educator (a parent), it qualifies as an educational third-party activity.

EXAMPLE 2: Types of educational third party activities: prescribed educational third party activity, non-prescribed educational third party activity the tutoring sessions are not recorded or assessed by the university. While beneficial, this type of support is informal and does not contribute to official academic records.

Table 41 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 48.

Table 41: Associations of healthcare third party activity (tab:41)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity</i>		<i>prescribed third party activity</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational third party activity</i>	generated	0..* <i>non-ratified educational information</i>
0..*	<i>educational third party activity</i>	requires	1..* <i>educational activity mandate</i>
1..*	<i>educational third party activity</i>	performs	1..* <i>educational third party activity</i>

Figure 48: Educational third party activity (UML representation)

7.8 Prescribed third party activity

Term: *prescribed third party activity* (*prescribed third party activity*)

Definition: *educational third party activity* prescribed by a *education professional*

EXAMPLE 1: A student, is struggling with academic writing. His professor and academic advisor identify a need for additional support and formally prescribe a third-party tutoring service to help him improve.

EXAMPLE 2: University-recommended tutoring services. The university’s disability office prescribes assistive technology training for a student with dyslexia. A business student receives a scholarship that includes mandatory career coaching from an external professional organization. The coaching sessions are a formal requirement and included in the student’s professional development record. A professor requires students to attend external research seminars or workshops hosted by partner universities.

Table 42 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 49.

Table 42: Associations of *prescribed third party activity* (tab:42)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>educational third party activity</i>				
Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>prescribed third party activity</i>	is prescribed by	1	<i>education professional</i>

Figure 49: Prescribed third party activity (UML representation)

7.9 Educational activity element

Term: *educational activity element* (*healthcare activity element*)

Definition: Element of *educational activity* that addresses one type of purpose

EXAMPLE:The course includes multiple educational activities, each of which consists of specific educational activity elements, designed to serve different learning purposes: weekly lecture, assigned textbook readings and research articles to reinforce lecture topics, exercises, a team-based project, weekly discussion forums, online quizzes, final exam, self-reflection assignments, peer review of coding assignments, providing constructive feedback.

Table 43 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 50.

Table 43: Associations of *educational activity element* (tab:43)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
			<i>educational investigation</i>
			<i>educational assessment</i>
			<i>educational instruction</i>
			<i>educational evaluation</i>
			<i>educational documenting</i>
			<i>educational communication</i>
			<i>educational activity management</i>
Component of		Aggregation of	
1	<i>educational activity</i>		
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	performs	0..* <i>educational activity element</i>

Figure 50: Educational activity element (UML representation)

7.10 Educational instruction

Term: *educational instruction* (healthcare treatment)

Definition: *educational activity element* intended to directly improve or maintain a *educational state*

NOTE: *educational instruction* is intended to contribute to fulfilling the assessed *educational need*.

EXAMPLE:Live coding demonstrations - a teacher walks through real coding examples in class, explaining each step and common mistakes. Students complete real-time coding exercises on an online platform that instantly provides feedback on errors and efficiency.

Table 44 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 51.

Table 44: Associations of *educational instruction* (tab:44)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>educational activity element</i>				
Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational instruction</i>	influences	1	<i>educational state</i>

Figure 51: Educational instruction (UML representation)

7.11 Educational investigation

Term: *educational investigation* (*healthcare investigation*)

Definition: *educational activity element* with the intention to clarify one or more *education conditions* of a *learner*

NOTE: *educational investigations* add and improve information about aspects of a *educational state*.

EXAMPLE: To clarify the root cause of students' difficulties and gain a better understanding of students' educational state, the teacher conducts educational investigations: a pre-test.

Table 45 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 52.

Table 45: Associations of *educational investigation* (tab:45)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>educational activity element</i>				
Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational investigation</i>	clarifies	1	<i>educational state</i>
0..*	<i>educational investigation</i>	reveals	0..*	<i>education condition</i>

Figure 52: Educational investigation (UML representation)

7.12 Educational activity management

Term: *educational activity management (healthcare activity management)*

Definition: *educational activity* element during which the status of *educational activities* in a *learning plan* are changed

NOTE: Examples statuses for *educational activities* are; planned, scheduled, resource allocated, ongoing, performed/finished, evaluated

EXAMPLE: The Capstone Project course where students design and prototype a real-world engineering solution over a semester requires structured management of educational activities to ensure timely progress and completion. At the start of the semester teacher defines project milestones, including proposal submission, prototype development, and final presentations. Each milestone is scheduled with specific deadlines. Once students start building their prototypes teacher monitors their progress through weekly check-ins and progress reports. After students submit their final prototype and report, their project phase is marked as completed in the course management system. Teacher grades final presentations and provides feedback, assessing each team's work based on predefined learning outcomes.

Table 46 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 53.

Table 46: Associations of *educational activity management* (tab:46)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity element</i>			
Component of		Aggregation of	
		0..*	<i>educational planning</i>
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational management activity</i> manages	1..*	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>educational management activity</i> changes statuses of healthcare activities in	1	<i>learning plan</i>

Figure 53: Educational activity management (UML representation)

7.13 Educational assessment

Term: *educational assessment (healthcare assessment)*

Definition: *educational activity element* where an opinion related to *education conditions* and/or *educational activities* is formed

EXAMPLE: Throughout the semester, educational assessments are conducted to form opinions on students' educational conditions (knowledge, skills, progress) and educational activities (assignments, participation, presentations).

Table 47 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 54.

Table 47: Associations of *educational assessment* (tab:47)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational activity element</i>	<i>educational needs assessment</i>

Figure 54: Educational assessment (UML representation)

7.14 Educational needs assessment

Term: *educational needs assessment* (*healthcare needs assessment*)

Definition: *educational assessment* during which a *education professional* considers a *learner's educational need* and determines the needed *educational activity*

NOTE 1: A *educational needs assessment* precedes *educational planning*.

NOTE 2: *educational needs assessments* should be performed in a dialogue with the *learner*. The responsibility for a *educational needs assessment* is held by a *education professional*.

NOTE 3: The *learner* interact with *education professionals* in *educational needs assessments* and also describe their opinions on which *educational activities* should be asked for in a *demand for education*.

EXAMPLE 1: Students complete a short argumentative essay, which is analyzed for structure, clarity, and citation skills. Based on this, the teacher determines who needs extra support in areas like thesis development or referencing.

EXAMPLE 2: A survey asks students to rate their confidence in different writing skills (e.g., paraphrasing,

argumentation) and to indicate what kind of support they think would help them.

Table 48 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 55.

Table 48: Associations of *educational needs assessment* (tab:48)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>educational assessment</i>				
Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>	precedes	0..1	<i>educational planning</i>
0..*	<i>learner desire</i>	is considered during	1..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	performs	0..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>
0..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>	identifies	0..*	<i>needed educational activity</i>
1	<i>educational need</i>	is considered during	0..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>

Figure 55: Educational needs assessment (UML representation)

7.15 Educational planning

Term: *educational planning* (healthcare planning)

Definition: Element of *educational activity management* where a *learning plan* is created or modified

EXAMPLE:The teacher supervises students in a master’s thesis seminar, where each student develops a research project over two semesters. Since students have different research interests, methodologies, and timelines, educational planning is crucial to ensure they stay on track.

Table 49 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 56.

Table 49: Associations of *educational planning* (tab:49)

Component of		Aggregation of	
1	<i>educational activity management</i>		
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational process</i>	is based upon	0..* <i>educational guideline</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	is result of	1..* <i>educational planning</i>
0..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>	precedes	0..1 <i>educational planning</i>

Figure 56: Educational planning (UML representation)

7.16 Educational evaluation

Term: *educational evaluation* (*healthcare evaluation*)

Definition: *educational activity element* where aspects of at least one other *educational activity element* is evaluated

NOTE 1: *educational evaluation* may be performed by all kinds of *educational actors*, including the *learner*.

NOTE 2: See also *learning process* outcome evaluation.

EXAMPLE: A teacher teaches a learning course that combines online lectures, in-person labs, and project-based assessments. To ensure the course remains effective, an educational evaluation is conducted at multiple levels.

Table 50 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 57.

Table 50: Associations of *educational evaluation* (tab:50)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity element</i>		<i>education process evaluation</i>	
		<i>educational process outcome evaluation</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational evaluation</i>	evaluates aspects of	1..* <i>educational activity</i>

Figure 57: Educational evaluation (UML representation)

7.17 Education process evaluation

Term: *education process evaluation* (*healthcare process evaluation*)

Definition: *educational evaluation* where *educational processes* are systematically assessed against requirements

NOTE 1: The outputs of *learning processes* are evaluated in a *educational process outcome evaluation*.

NOTE 2: Requirements are defined as a combination of needs and expectations that are stated, generally implied or obligatory. The needs can be represented by, for example, target conditions, goals for resource consumption, compliance to guidelines, etc. The expectations can be represented by the perceptions of the outcomes from each of the involved *educational actor* perspective (i.e. *learner* and *education professionals*).

EXAMPLE: A university offers a master’s program, which includes coursework, lab sessions, industry projects, and a final thesis. To ensure the program meets academic and industry standards, an education process evaluation is conducted. The university reviews course syllabi, faculty qualifications, and assessment methods to verify alignment with accreditation guidelines.

Table 51 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 58.

Table 51: Associations of *education process evaluation* (tab:51)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational evaluation</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>education process evaluation</i>	evaluates	1..* <i>educational process</i>

Figure 58: Educational process evaluation (UML representation)

7.18 Educational process outcome evaluation

Term: *educational process outcome evaluation (clinical process outcome evaluation)*

Definition: *educational evaluation* where the effects of a *learning process* on a *educational state* are assessed against the target condition and/or a *education condition* representing the input *educational state*

NOTE 1: The *learner* and *education professionals* are the main contributors to a *educational process outcome evaluation*.

NOTE 2: The target condition represents a requirement for the *learning process*.

EXAMPLE 1: Comparison of student competence before and after the course

EXAMPLE 2: A university offers a capstone projects. The goal of the capstone is for students to apply knowledge to solve real-world problems. An educational process outcome evaluation is conducted to assess whether the learning process achieved its intended outcomes.

Table 52 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 59.

Table 52: Associations of *educational process outcome evaluation* (tab:52)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational evaluation</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational process outcome evaluation</i>	evaluates outcome of	1 <i>learning process</i>
1..*	<i>target educational condition</i>	is input to	0..* <i>educational process outcome evaluation</i>
0..*	<i>resultant educational condition</i>	is input to	0..* <i>educational process outcome evaluation</i>

Figure 59: Educational process outcome evaluation (UML representation)

7.19 Educational documenting

Term: *educational documenting* (*healthcare documenting*)

Definition: *educational activity element* where *educational records* are created or maintained

EXAMPLE 1: In a university setting, educational documenting refers to the process of creating and maintaining records related to a student’s learning progress, assessments, and achievements.

EXAMPLE 2: Assignment scores, feedback, and participation records, feedback, and revisions, the thesis defense process

Table 53 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 60.

Table 53: Associations of *educational documenting* (tab:53)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity element</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational documenting</i>	maintains	1..* <i>educational record</i>

Figure 60: Educational documenting (UML representation)

7.20 Educational communication

Term: *educational communication* (*healthcare communication*)

Definition: *educational activity element* where at least two *educational actors* communicate

EXAMPLE: Educational communication refers to structured interactions between students, faculty, advisors, and other educational actors to facilitate learning and academic progress.

Table 54 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 61.

Table 54: Associations of *educational communication* (tab:54)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational activity element</i>	

Figure 61: Educational communication (UML representation)

7.21 Automated education

Term: *automated education* (*automated healthcare*)

Definition: Method of delivering *education* initiated by a responsible *educational actor* and there after delivered automatically by an *intelligent educational technology*

NOTE: *automated education* is not a *educational activity* in its own right since the *intelligent educational technology* doesn't have the capacity to be responsible. It is the *educational actor* who initiates and reviews the *automated education* that is responsible for safe use of the *intelligent educational technology*.

EXAMPLE: Automated education refers to learning experiences that are initiated by an instructor or institution but delivered automatically by intelligent educational technologies. These systems personalize learning, adjust content based on student performance, and provide automated feedback.

Table 55 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 62.

Table 55: Associations of *automated education* (tab:55)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	initiated during	1	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	reviewed during	0..*	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	terminated during	0..1	<i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	results in	0..*	<i>non-ratified educational information</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	is responsible for	0..*	<i>automated education</i>
1	<i>intelligent educational technology</i>	delivers	0..*	<i>automated education</i>

Figure 62: Automated education (UML representation)

7.22 Educational resource

Term: *educational resource* (*healthcare resource*)

Definition: Resource needed to perform *educational activities*

EXAMPLE: An educational resource refers to any material, tool, or infrastructure needed to perform educational activities effectively. These resources can be digital (e.g., learning platforms, e-books, AI tutors) or physical (e.g., classrooms, lab equipment, textbooks).

Table 56 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 63.

Table 56: Associations of *educational resource* (tab:56)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>resource</i>		<i>educational personnel</i>	
		<i>point of learning</i>	
		<i>educational product</i>	
		<i>educational device</i>	
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	requires	1..* <i>educational resource</i>
1..*	<i>educational management</i>	direct and control the supply and use of	1..* <i>educational resource</i>
0..*	<i>educational funds</i>	is funding	0..* <i>educational resource</i>

Figure 63: Educational resource (UML representation)

7.23 Point of learning

Term: *point of learning* (*point of care*)

Definition: Location where direct *educational activities* are performed

NOTE: Location refers to the geographical location of the *learner*.

EXAMPLE:Laboratories, libraries, learning centers, companies, stades, computer classes

Table 57 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 64.

Table 57: Associations of *point of learning* (tab:57)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational resource</i>	

Figure 64: Point of learning (UML representation)

7.24 Intelligent educational technology

Term: *intelligent educational technology* (*automatic medical device*)

Definition: *educational device* capable of performing automated *educational activities*

EXAMPLE: Intelligent educational technology refers to advanced digital tools and systems that use artificial intelligence, machine learning, or automation to enhance teaching and learning processes.

Table 58 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 65.

Table 58: Associations of *intelligent educational technology* (tab:58)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational device</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1 <i>intelligent educational technology</i>	delivers	0..*	<i>automated education</i>

Figure 65: Intelligent educational technology (UML representation)

7.25 Educational resource management

Term: *educational resource management* (*healthcare resource management*)

Definition: Activities to direct and control the supply and use of the *educational resources* required to perform *educational activities*

EXAMPLE: Learning management systems (LMS), digital library systems, classroom and facility scheduling, faculty workload management, student information systems

Table 59 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 66.

Table 59: Associations of *educational resource management* (tab:59)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational management resource</i>	direct and control the supply and use of	1..*	<i>educational resource</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	requires	0..*	<i>educational management resource</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	performs	0..*	<i>educational management resource</i>

Figure 66: Educational resource management (UML representation)

7.26 Educational funds

Term: *educational funds (healthcare funds)*

Definition: Resource provided for funding *education* delivery

EXAMPLE 1: Educational funds refer to financial resources allocated to support the delivery of education, including student tuition assistance, institutional funding, research grants, and infrastructure development. These funds can come from government agencies, private organizations, donors, or internal institutional budgets.

EXAMPLE 2: Government grants, research grants

Table 60 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 67.

Table 60: Associations of *educational funds* (tab:60)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
<i>resource</i>				
Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>education</i>	is financed by	0..*	<i>educational funds</i>
0..*	<i>educational actor</i>	provides	0..*	<i>educational funds</i>
0..*	<i>educational funds</i>	is funding	0..*	<i>educational resource</i>

Figure 67: Educational funds (UML representation)

8 Concepts related to processes

8.1 General

A model showing the associations between the process related concepts and the other concepts defined in this International Standard is shown in Figure 68. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 68: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to process

8.2 Educational process

Term: *educational process* (healthcare process)

Synonyms: learning process

Definition: Set of interrelated or interacting *educational activities* which transforms inputs into outputs

NOTE 1: The main type of *educational process* is the *learning process* that has an educational state as input and output and includes all activities related to one or more specified *education issues*.

NOTE 2: A *educational process* is not by definition restricted to one *educator* or any other organizational unit borders.

EXAMPLE: An educational process is a structured series of interrelated educational activities that transform an initial educational state (input) into a desired learning objective (output). It includes all activities related to a specific educational issue and is not limited to a single educator or institution.

Table 61 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 69.

Table 61: Associations of *educational process* (tab:61)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>process</i>		<i>learning process</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..1	<i>educational process</i>	1..0	<i>educational activity</i>
		0..*	<i>educational process</i>
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational process</i>	is performed for	1 <i>learner</i>
0..*	<i>educational process</i>	is planned in	0..* <i>learning plan</i>
0..*	<i>education process evaluation</i>	evaluates	1..* <i>educational process</i>
1..*	<i>educational process</i>	is documented in	0..* <i>educational record</i>
1..*	<i>educational process</i>	has output	0..1 <i>output educational state</i>
1..*	<i>educational process</i>	provides feedback to	0..1 <i>educational quality management</i>
1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	regulates	1..* <i>educational process</i>
0..1	<i>input educational state</i>	is input to	1 <i>educational process</i>
0..1	<i>educational administration</i>	is supporting	1..* <i>educational process</i>
0..1	<i>educational quality management</i>	controls quality of	1..* <i>educational process</i>
0..*	<i>adverse educational event</i>	influences	1..* <i>educational process</i>
0..1	<i>educational service</i>	is the result of	1 <i>educational process</i>

Figure 69: Educational process (UML representation)

8.3 Learning process

Term: *learning process* (clinical process)

Definition: *educational process* encompassing all *education provider activities* and other prescribed *educational activity* that addresses identified or specified *education issues*

NOTE 1: As such, a *learning process* is a set of interrelated or interacting *educational activities*, which are performed for a *learner* with one or more *education issues*.

NOTE 2: The primary input and output to a *learning process* is the *educational state*.

NOTE 3: In a *learning process* a *learner* and *education professionals* interact in all types of *educational activities*.

NOTE 4: A *learning process* comprises all kinds of *educational activities*, mainly *education provider activities*, but also *self-learning activities* as prescribed or recommended by *education professionals*

NOTE 5: The *learning process* can be regarded as the key type of *process* to support continuity of education from the perspective of the *learner*.

NOTE 6: *learning processes* are the essential, central and most important type of *educational processes*.

EXAMPLE: A learning process is a structured set of educational activities that involve interactions between learners and education professionals to address specific educational issues. It includes both education provider activities (e.g., lectures, assessments, mentoring) and prescribed self-learning activities (e.g., assigned readings, projects).

Table 62 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 70.

Table 62: Associations of *learning process* (tab:62)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational process</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>learning process</i>	addresses	1..* <i>education issue</i>
1..*	<i>learning process</i>	includes	1..* <i>mandated period of education</i>
1	<i>learning process episode</i>	is time interval for	1 <i>learning process</i>
1	<i>learning process</i>	has	0..1 <i>educational process interest</i>
0..*	<i>educational process outcome evaluation</i>	evaluates outcome of	1 <i>learning process</i>
0..1	<i>educational initial contact</i>	establishes	1 <i>learning process</i>

Figure 70: Learning process (UML representation)

8.4 Educational quality management

Term: *educational quality management (healthcare quality management)*

Synonyms: academic governance

Definition: Coordinated activities to direct and control a *educational organization* with regard to quality

NOTE 1: The *learning processes* are the most important type of *educational processes* related to *educational quality management*.

NOTE 2: *educational quality management* activities include the establishment of a quality policy, setting quality objectives, the performance of audits, evaluation and a feedback loop for quality improvement, all

resulting in quality assurance.

EXAMPLE 1: Directing and controlling the fulfilment of requirements in quality criteria repositories, changing behaviour of educational professionals.

EXAMPLE 2: Educational quality management (also referred to as academic governance) involves coordinated activities to ensure the quality of education in a university or educational institution. It focuses on improving learning processes, assessing outcomes, and maintaining academic standards.

Table 63 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 71.

Table 63: Associations of *educational quality management* (tab:63)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..1	<i>educational management quality</i>	controls quality of	1..*	<i>educational process</i>
1	<i>educational organization</i>	performs	1..*	<i>educational quality management</i>
1..*	<i>educational process</i>	provides feedback to	0..1	<i>educational quality management</i>

Figure 71: Educational quality management (UML representation)

8.5 Educational administration

Term: *educational administration (healthcare administration)*

Definition: Administrative activities related to *educational processes*

NOTE: Administrative activities are indirect activities in a *educational process* and include support and management.

EXAMPLE 1: Budgeting and resource allocation, organizational structure, non-academic documentation, administrative activity management, resource management, etc.

EXAMPLE 2: Educational administration refers to administrative activities that support and manage educational processes. These activities are indirect but essential for ensuring smooth operations, policy enforcement, and institutional efficiency.

Table 64 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 72.

Table 64: Associations of *educational administration* (tab:64)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..1	<i>educational administration</i>	is supporting	1..*	<i>educational process</i>

Figure 72: Educational administration (UML representation)

8.6 Adverse educational event

Term: *adverse educational event* (*adverse event*)

Definition: Unintended event that has negative influence upon *educational processes*

NOTE 1: An *adverse educational events* can occur during appropriate *educational activities*.

NOTE 2: *adverse educational events* events may cause harm to the educational process or student outcomes.

EXAMPLE 1: A student is experiencing stress or anxiety due to a difficult exam. An instructional method that, although widely recommended, leads to confusion or misunderstanding among students. An accident during a school activity that disrupts the learning environment. A technical issue during an online class that prevents effective teaching and learning.

EXAMPLE 2: An adverse educational event is an unintended event that negatively impacts educational processes or student outcomes. These events may occur even during properly planned educational activities and can disrupt learning, assessment, or overall academic progress: a learning management system (LMS) crashes, a scheduled virtual lecture fails, incorrect grading of student work due to a mistake in an automated grading system, course schedule conflicts.

Table 65 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 73.

Table 65: Associations of *adverse educational event* (tab:65)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>unintended event</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>adverse educational event</i>	influences	1..* <i>educational process</i>
1	<i>adverse educational event</i>	requires	1 <i>adverse educational event management</i>

Figure 73: Adverse educational event (UML representation)

8.7 Adverse educational event management

Term: *adverse educational event management* (*adverse event management*)

Definition: Set of *educational activities* performed in response to an *adverse educational event*

NOTE: The purposes for *adverse educational event management* are usually two: one is to reverse the effect or minimize the consequences of the *adverse educational event*, another one is to prevent the kind of *adverse educational event* in the future.

EXAMPLE: During a scheduled online final exam, the university’s exam platform crashes, preventing students from submitting their answers.

Table 66 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 74.

Table 66: Associations of *adverse educational event management* (tab:66)

Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>educational activity</i>
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>adverse educational event</i>	requires	1 <i>adverse educational event management</i>

Figure 74: Adverse educational event management (UML representation)

8.8 Educational service

Term: *educational service* (*healthcare service*)

Definition: Service that is the result of an *educational process*

NOTE: Comprehensive *educational services* intended for specified *education issues* are results of *learning processes*.

EXAMPLE 1:Assessment and feedback report.

EXAMPLE 2:An educational service is a service that results from an educational process, aiming to address specific learning needs or educational issues of students: bachelor’s, master’s, or PhD programs; coursera, moodle, e-learning portals; guidance on course selection and career paths; university career fairs, internship placements, or resume workshops.

Table 67 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 75.

Table 67: Associations of *educational service* (tab:67)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..1	<i>educational service</i>	is the result of	1	<i>educational process</i>
1..*	<i>educational service</i>	is listed in	1..*	<i>educational service directory</i>
1	<i>educational period mandate</i>	commissions	1..*	<i>educational service</i>

Figure 75: Educational service (UML representation)

8.9 Educational service directory

Term: *educational service directory* (*healthcare service directory*)

Definition: Directory of the types of *educational services* offered by one or more *educators*

EXAMPLE:An educational service directory is a structured listing of the types of educational services offered by one or more educators or educational institutions: university course catalog detailing undergraduate and graduate courses. A university’s official degree program listing. University e-learning platforms (e.g., Moodle, Coursera partnerships). Tutoring services, mental health counseling, career services. University faculty directory with research interests and publications. Listings of internship placements, employer partnerships, and career advising services. University library databases, digital repositories, and citation tools. University sports teams, debate clubs.

Table 68 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 76.

Table 68: Associations of *educational service directory* (tab:68)

Association from					Association name	Association to			
1..*	<i>educational service</i>		is listed in	1..*		<i>educational service directory</i>			

Figure 76: Educational service directory (UML representation)

9 Concepts related to educational planning

9.1 General

A model showing the associations between the concepts related to the use of knowledge and decision support in *continuity of education* and the other concepts defined in this International Standard is shown in Figure 77. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 77: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to educational planning

9.2 Learning plan

Term: *learning plan* (*care plan*)

Definition: Dynamic, personalized plan including identified *needed educational activity*, *learning objectives* and *educational goals*, relating to one or more specified *education issues* in a *educational process*

NOTE 1: A *learning plan* may be recorded in one or more *educational records*

NOTE 2: A *learning plan* could be subdivided from different perspectives by different constraints. One example is *unidisciplinary learning plan*, for example, a nursing care plan with the constraint of only one specific *education professional* involved. Other examples of specific constraints for a *learning plan* are: care plan to address one *education issue*, one *education condition*, one *educational contact*, one *learning process*, *educational activities* to be performed by one *educator*, etc.

NOTE 3: The *educational activities* in a *learning plan* follow a life cycle. Examples of statuses of such a life cycle are: ‘planned’, ‘performed’, ‘cancelled’, etc.; all of these statuses are included in the care plan.

EXAMPLE: A learning plan is a dynamic, personalized roadmap that outlines the educational activities, learning objectives, and academic goals tailored to address one or more specific learning needs within an educational process: A student with special learning accommodations receives a PLP with additional tutoring sessions and extended deadlines. A PhD candidate follows a PDP including conference presentations, skill-building workshops, and teaching experience. A detailed schedule and objectives for completing a final research project. A student working on their capstone project outlines research phases, writing milestones, and advisor meetings.

Table 69 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 78.

Table 69: Associations of *learning plan* (tab:69)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>unidisciplinary learning plan</i>	
		<i>multi-professional educational plan</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	0..*	<i>learning plan</i>
		1..*	<i>educational activity</i>
		0..*	<i>educational activity package</i>
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	complies with	0..* <i>educational guideline</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	implements	0..* <i>educational protocol</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	icare plans based upon	0..* <i>core learning plan</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	addresscare planses	1..* <i>education issue</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	addresses	0..* <i>educational thread</i>
1..*	<i>learning plan</i>	targets	1..* <i>learning objective</i>
1..*	<i>learning plan</i>	targets	1..* <i>educational goal</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	is result of	1..* <i>educational planning</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	applies	0..* <i>learning plan</i>
0..*	<i>educational process</i>	is planned in	0..* <i>learning plan</i>
0..*	<i>educational appointment</i>	is scheduled in	0..1 <i>learning plan</i>

Figure 78: Educational plan (UML diagram)

9.3 Unidisciplinary learning plan

Term: *unidisciplinary learning plan* (*uniprofessional care plan*)

Synonyms: unidisciplinary education plan

Deprecated term: *learning plan*

Definition: *learning plan* limited to those *educator* activities performed by *education professionals* having the same *education professional* entitlement

EXAMPLE: A learning plan designed specifically for medical students training to become general practitioners, with all educational activities conducted by licensed medical doctors. Engineering course structure – a plan where all subjects and practical sessions in a civil engineering program are taught solely by civil engineers, without input from other disciplines. Computer science program – a learning plan where all teaching activities related to programming, data structures, and artificial intelligence are conducted solely by computer scientists or software engineers.

Table 70 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 79

Table 70: Associations of *unidisciplinary learning plan* (tab:70)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>learning plan</i>	

Figure 79: Unidisciplinary learning plan (UML diagram)

9.4 Multi-professional educational plan

Term: *multi-professional educational plan (multi-professional care plan)*

Synonyms: multi-professional healthcare plan, multi-disciplinary care plan

Definition: *learning plan* encompassing *education provider activities* performed by *education professionals* having different *educational professional entitlements*

EXAMPLE: A collaborative learning plan where medical students, nursing students, and pharmacy students participate in shared simulations and case studies to enhance teamwork in patient care. Engineering business joint curriculum – a multi-professional learning plan where engineering students and business students co-develop technology-based startup projects, integrating technical knowledge with entrepreneurship skills.

Table 71 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 80

Table 71: Associations of *multi-professional educational plan* (tab:71)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>learning plan</i>	

Figure 80: Multi-professional educational plan (UML diagram)

9.5 Core learning plan

Term: *core learning plan* (*core care plan*)

Synonyms: standardized *learning plan*

Definition: Reusable content and structure for a potential *learning plan* for a specified set of circumstances

NOTE 1: A *core learning plan* is usually based upon knowledge in clinical guidelines (including protocols).

NOTE 2: Core care plans can be applied in care planning as a clinical process management method.

NOTE 3: A core care plan may include advanced formulated schemes for recommended healthcare activities.

EXAMPLE: Engineering fundamentals learning plan – a core curriculum that provides essential knowledge in physics, mathematics, and technical drawing, serving as the foundation for specialized engineering fields.

Table 72 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 81.

Table 72: Associations of *core learning plan* (tab:72)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..1	<i>educational pathway</i>	informs	1..*	<i>core learning plan</i>
1..*	<i>educational organization</i>	adopts	0..*	<i>core learning plan</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	is based upon	0..*	<i>core learning plan</i>

Figure 81: Core learning plan (UML diagram)

9.6 Educational guideline

Term: *educational guideline* (*clinical guideline*)

Synonyms: care guideline

Definition: Set of systematically developed statements to assist the decisions made by *educational actors* about *educational activities* to be performed with regard to specified *education issues*

NOTE: *educational guidelines* should be structured and contain standard criteria and indicators for measurement.

EXAMPLE 1: Higher education accreditation standards – national or international guidelines that define quality assurance criteria for universities, including curriculum design, faculty qualifications, and student assessment methods.

EXAMPLE 2: STEM curriculum frameworks – guidelines developed by academic institutions or professional organizations to ensure consistency in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics education.

EXAMPLE 3: Capstone project and thesis requirements – structured guidelines for undergraduate and graduate students outlining expectations, assessment rubrics, and best practices for completing final-year projects or theses.

Table 73 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 82.

Table 73: Associations of *educational guideline* (tab:73)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>educational protocol</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational guideline</i>	is centered on	1..* <i>education issue</i>
0..*	<i>educational pathway</i>	refers to	1..* <i>educational guideline</i>
0..*	<i>educational actor</i>	makes decisions assisted by	0..* <i>educational guideline</i>
0..*	<i>educational planning</i>	is based upon	0..* <i>educational guideline</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	complies with	0..* <i>educational guideline</i>

Figure 82: Educational guideline (UML diagram)

9.7 Educational protocol

Term: *educational protocol* (*protocol*)

Definition: Customized *educational guideline*

NOTE 1: A *educational protocols* is more precise than a *educational guideline*.

NOTE 2: *educational protocols* are often presented in a formal manner with respect to the expected behaviours and roles of *educational actors*.

EXAMPLE 1: Medical school clinical training protocol – a detailed set of steps medical students must follow when interacting with patients, including history-taking, diagnostic procedures, and ethical considerations.

EXAMPLE 2: Examination conduct protocol – a formalized document specifying rules for invigilators, students, and faculty regarding exam administration, cheating prevention, and accommodations.

EXAMPLE 3: Interdisciplinary project collaboration protocol – a structured process outlining the roles and responsibilities of students and faculty from different disciplines working on joint research or innovation projects.

Table 74 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 83.

Table 74: Associations of *educational protocol* (tab:74)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational guideline</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	implements	0..* <i>educational protocol</i>

Figure 83: Educational protocol (UML diagram)

9.8 Educational pathway

Term: *educational pathway (clinical pathway)*

Synonyms: care pathway, care map, pathway of care

Definition: Pathway for the *educational activities* informing the content of *core learning plans*

NOTE 1: The concept *educational pathway* includes subtypes, for example, ‘integrated care pathways’, ‘multidisciplinary pathways of care’, ‘collaborative care pathways’.

NOTE 2: *educational pathways* are designed to support *educational administration* and *educational resource management*. They provide detailed guidance for each stage in the management of a patient (treatments, interventions, etc.).

EXAMPLE:Engineering degree pathway – A structured academic plan outlining key milestones, including fundamental courses, hands-on lab work, internships, and capstone projects leading to professional certification.

Table 75 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 84.

Table 75: Associations of *educational pathway* (tab:75)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational pathway</i>	refers to	1..*	<i>educational guideline</i>
0..1	<i>educational pathway</i>	informs	1..*	<i>core learning plan</i>
0..*	<i>educational pathway</i>	addresses	1..*	<i>education condition</i>
1..*	<i>education condition</i>	governs the choice of	0..*	<i>educational pathway</i>

Figure 84: Educational pathway (UML diagram)

9.9 Learning objective

Term: *learning objective (health objective)*

Synonyms: intended outcome

Definition: Desired ultimate achievement of a *educational process* addressing *educational needs*

NOTE: A *learning objective* could be expressed as one or several target conditions to be reached within a specified date and time.

EXAMPLE: Computer science learning objective – students will design, implement, and test software solutions using industry-standard programming languages and methodologies.

Table 76 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 85.

Table 76: Associations of *learning objective* (tab:76)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>learning objective</i>	addresses	1..*	<i>educational need</i>
1..*	<i>educational goal</i>	contributes to achievement of	1..*	<i>learning objective</i>
0..*	<i>target educational condition</i>	represents	0..*	<i>learning objective</i>
1..*	<i>learning plan</i>	targets	1..*	<i>learning objective</i>

Figure 85: Learning objective (UML diagram)

9.10 Educational goal

Term: *educational goal (healthcare goal)*

Definition: Desired achievement of one or more *educational activities*, considered as an intermediate operational step to reach a specific *learning objective*

NOTE: A *educational goal* could be expressed as one or several *target educational conditions* to be reached within a specified date and time.

EXAMPLE:Engineering course educational goal – students will complete and submit a working prototype of a solar-powered device as part of their final project.

Table 77 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 86.

Table 77: Associations of *educational goal* (tab:77)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational goal</i>	contributes to achievement of	1..*	<i>learning objective</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	targets	1..*	<i>educational goal</i>
1..*	<i>learning plan</i>	targets	1..*	<i>educational goal</i>
0..*	<i>target educational condition</i>	represents	0..*	<i>educational goal</i>
0..*	<i>educational approach</i>	addresses	1	<i>educational goal</i>

Figure 86: Educational goal (UML diagram)

9.11 Educational activity package

Term: *educational activity package* (*healthcare activity bundle*)

Definition: Set of *educational activities*

NOTE: A healthcare activity bundle may be delineated using a health thread comprising healthcare activities.

EXAMPLE 1:Medical school educational activity package – A set of activities including anatomy lectures, virtual dissections, and hands-on clinical simulations to teach human physiology.

EXAMPLE 2:Engineering lab activity package – a series of experiments and design challenges focused on electrical circuit building and testing.

Table 78 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 87.

Table 78: Associations of *educational activity package* (tab:78)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
			<i>needed educational activity</i>
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..*	<i>educational activity package</i>	0..*	<i>educational activity package</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity</i>

Figure 87: *educational activity package* (UML diagram)

9.12 Needed educational activity

Term: *needed educational activity* (*needed healthcare activity*)

Synonyms: needed care activity, healthcare need, care need

Definition: *educational activity packages* which includes those *educational activities* assessed as needed to address specified health need

NOTE 1: Needed *educational activity* is the *educational activity* that is assessed by *education professionals* to be motivated/indicated by the *educational need*.

NOTE 2: Needed *educational activity* is the outcome of *education* needs assessments performed by *education professionals*. Needed *educational activity* can be identified by any mandated *education professional* performing *educational needs assessment* for a *learner*.

NOTE 3: Needed *educational activity* is managed in a *learning plan*.

EXAMPLE 1:Engineering needed educational activity – an assessment of a student’s skill in CAD (Computer-Aided Design) could lead to a needed educational activity involving further training in 3D modeling and software proficiency.

EXAMPLE 2:Computer science needed educational activity – if a student is weak in programming, they may be assigned additional coding exercises, pair programming sessions, or online coding challenges to improve their skills.

Table 79 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 88.

Table 79: Associations of *needed educational activity* (tab:79)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity package</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>	identifies	0..* <i>needed educational activity</i>
1..*	<i>needed educational activity</i>	addresses	1..* <i>educational need</i>

Figure 88: Needed educational activity (UML diagram)

10 Concepts related to time

10.1 General

A model showing the associations between the time-related concepts in *continuity of education* and the other concepts defined in this International Standard is shown in Figure 89. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 89: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to time

10.2 Education related period

Term: *education related period* (health related period)

Definition: Time interval related to the education of a *learner* and/or the provision of educational

services for that *learner*

NOTE 1: An *education related period* may be specialized in relation to a number of situations – a specific *learning process*, *education professional*, a specific department, a specific *education issue*, etc.

NOTE 2: An *education related period* is delineated by a 'start date and time' and an 'end date and time'. While the statement of the start date is generally easy by definition, the identification of the end date may be subject to specific rules that have to be agreed upon locally.

EXAMPLE 1: Semester-based education related period – the time frame of a university semester, beginning from the first day of classes to the last day of final exams. This period may include specific milestones like midterm evaluations or project submissions.

EXAMPLE 2: Course enrollment education related period – the specific period within which a student is enrolled in a particular course, starting with the registration and orientation process and ending with course completion and assessment.

EXAMPLE 3: Research project education related period – a defined period in which students are involved in collaborative or individual research projects, from the planning stages through to final presentation or publication.

Table 80 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 90.

Table 80: Associations of *education related period* (tab:80)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>mandated period of education</i>	
		<i>educational activity period</i>	
		<i>educational activity delay</i>	
		<i>episode of learning support</i>	
		<i>learning process episode</i>	
		<i>educational condition period</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..1	<i>education related period</i>	0..*	<i>education related period</i>

Figure 90: Education related period (UML diagram)

10.3 Mandated period of education

Term: *mandated period of education* (*mandated period of care*)

Synonyms: commissioned period of education

Definition: Set of *educational activity periods* where a *educator* is mandated to perform the *educational activities* required to address specific *educational needs*

NOTE 1: The *mandated period of education* is focused upon the framework of a commitment of the provider as well as the mandate from the *learner*, which means that the roles and responsibilities of both the interacting parties are respected.

NOTE 2: Whenever the *educator* considered in a *mandated period of education* is a *educational organization*, this *mandated period of education* encompasses all *educational activity periods* with *education professionals* who have a role in that *educational organization*.

NOTE 3: A *mandated period of education* may be part of another *mandated period of education*.

EXAMPLE 1: A school term, a series of tutoring sessions at an educational center.

EXAMPLE 2: Graduate thesis mandated period of education – the period during which graduate students are expected to work on their thesis projects. This includes specific milestones such as proposal submission, research activity, and final defense, all mandated by the university as part of the graduate program.

EXAMPLE 3: Engineering design project mandated period of education – a required period for engineering students to work on their capstone design projects, which are assessed by faculty mentors to meet specific academic and professional standards.

Table 81 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 91.

Table 81: Associations of *mandated period of education* (tab:81)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education related period</i>			
Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>educational activity period</i>
		1..*	<i>educational activity delay</i>
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1	<i>educational period mandate</i>	1	<i>mandated period of education</i>

Figure 91: Mandated period of education (UML diagram)

10.4 Educational activity period

Term: *educational activity period* (healthcare activity period)

Definition: Time interval during which *educational activities* are performed for a *learner*

EXAMPLE 1:Lecture educational activity period – the specific time frame during which a professor delivers a lecture to a class of students.

EXAMPLE 2:Examination educational activity period – a specific time interval when students take exams to assess their understanding of the course material, for example, a two-hour written exam for a final project.

EXAMPLE 3:Internship educational activity period – a designated period when a student participates in an internship or practical placement in a professional setting, like a six-week internship in a healthcare clinic.

Table 82 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 92.

Table 82: Associations of *educational activity period* (tab:82)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education related period</i>		<i>educational contact period</i>	
		<i>indirect educational activity period</i>	
		<i>self-study period</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
1..*	<i>mandated period of education</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity period element</i>
0..1	<i>learning process episode</i>		
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1	<i>educational activity period</i>	0..1	<i>educational appointment</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	0..*	<i>educational activity period</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	1	<i>educational activity period</i>
0..*	<i>educational record</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity period</i>

Figure 92: Educational activity period (UML diagram)

10.5 Educational contact period

Term: *educational contact period* (*contact period*)

Definition: *educational activity period* during which a *educational contact* occurs

NOTE: Since during a contact, more than one *education issue* may be addressed, it may relate to more than one *educational process* and more than one *episode of learning support*.

EXAMPLE 1: Classroom educational contact period – the time during which a student attends a lecture or seminar and directly interacts with the professor or instructor.

EXAMPLE 2: Internship educational contact period – a set time during which a student interacts with their mentor or supervisor in a professional setting, such as a weekly meeting or check-in during a 6-month

internship.

EXAMPLE 3:Online educational contact period – a live, synchronous online session in which students interact with the instructor, such as a 1-hour virtual seminar.

EXAMPLE 4:Group study educational contact period – the time during which students collaborate in study groups under the guidance of a faculty member

Table 83 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 93.

Table 83: Associations of *educational contact period* (tab:83)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity period</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational contact</i>	takes place during	1 <i>educational contact period</i>

Figure 93: Educational contact period (UML diagram)

10.6 Educational contact

Term: *educational contact* (*contact*)

Definition: Interaction between a *learner* and one or more *educational personnel*

EXAMPLE 1:Lecture educational contact – the interaction between a student and the professor during a class session, where the professor provides instructional content, and students can ask questions or engage in discussions.

EXAMPLE 2:Online learning educational contact – an interaction that occurs during live virtual sessions, such as a student participating in an online lecture, seminar, or group discussion via video conferencing with a professor.

EXAMPLE 3:Workshop educational contact – a session where a student interacts with an instructor or workshop leader to practice a skill or engage in an activity, such as a hands-on art workshop.

Table 84 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 94.

Table 84: Associations of *educational contact* (tab:84)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>educational initial contact</i>	
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational contact</i>	takes place during	1 <i>educational contact period</i>
1	<i>learner</i>	participates in	0..* <i>educational contact</i>
1..*	<i>educational personnel</i>	participates in	0..* <i>educational contact</i>
0..1	<i>referral</i>	initiates	0..1 <i>educational contact</i>
0..1	<i>educational appointment</i>	is appointment for	1 <i>educational contact</i>

Figure 94: Educational contact (UML diagram)

10.7 Educational initial contact

Term: *educational initial contact* (*initial contact*)

Definition: *educational contact* during which an *learning process* is initiated

EXAMPLE 1: Internship placement educational initial contact – the first meeting between a student and their internship supervisor, where the scope of the internship, roles, and responsibilities are clarified, marking the beginning of the learning experience in a professional setting.

EXAMPLE 2: Initial online course educational contact – the first engagement in an online course, such as an introductory video or welcome message from the instructor, where the course structure, objectives, and expectations are introduced to the students.

EXAMPLE 3: Research Project Educational Initial Contact – The first meeting between a research supervisor and a student, where the research objectives, expectations, and methods are outlined, initiating the student’s research journey.

Table 85 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 95.

Table 85: Associations of *educational initial contact* (tab:85)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational contact</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..1	<i>educational initial contact</i>	establishes	1 <i>learning process</i>
0..1	<i>demand for initial contact</i>	results in	0..1 <i>educational initial contact</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	arranges	0..* <i>educational initial contact</i>

Figure 95: Educational initial contact (UML diagram)

10.8 Indirect educational activity period

Term: *indirect educational activity period* (*indirect healthcare activity period*)

Definition: *educational activity period* without the involvement of the *learner*

EXAMPLE 1: The period where educational activities are performed without the presence of the student in order to decide whether a referral or a demand for initial contact should be accepted or not

EXAMPLE 2: Time spent working on assignments, projects, or assessments submitted by a student

EXAMPLE 3: Course planning indirect educational activity period – the time when a professor is preparing course materials, designing assessments, or updating the syllabus for an upcoming semester, without direct interaction with the students.

EXAMPLE 4: Grading and assessment indirect educational activity period – the time a professor spends grading assignments, exams, or projects, providing feedback, and assessing the students’ performance, which indirectly contributes to the learners’ educational experience.

EXAMPLE 5: Curriculum Development Indirect Educational Activity Period – The period when a department or faculty team is revising or developing a new curriculum, ensuring it aligns with educational standards and goals, without direct involvement of the students.

EXAMPLE 6: Program evaluation indirect educational activity period – the time spent evaluating the effectiveness of educational programs through analysis of student performance, surveys, and feedback, which helps improve the learning environment, but does not directly involve students.

Table 86 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 96.

Table 86: Associations of *indirect educational activity period* (tab:86)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational activity period</i>	

Figure 96: Indirect educational activity period (UML diagram)

10.9 Self-study period

Term: *self-study period* (*self-care period*)

Definition: *educational activity period* where *prescribed self-learning* is performed

EXAMPLE 1:Assigned reading self-study period – the time when a student reads course materials or textbooks as prescribed by the professor to prepare for lectures or exams, such as reading a chapter from a history textbook in preparation for an upcoming class.

EXAMPLE 2:Homework self-study period – a period in which a student completes assignments or problem sets on their own, such as working on mathematics exercises or writing a research paper.

EXAMPLE 3:Project work self-study period – when a student independently works on a project or thesis, researching, planning, and writing without direct guidance from an instructor, like developing a final project for a graphic design course.

EXAMPLE 4:Online course self-study period – a time spent by a student in an online learning environment to complete lessons, watch instructional videos, or take quizzes, such as working through an online module in a business administration course.

Table 87 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 97.

Table 87: Associations of *self-study period* (tab:87)

Specialization of	Generalization of	
<i>educational activity period</i>		
Association from	Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>prescribed self-learning</i>	takes place during
		1
		<i>self-study period</i>

Figure 97: Self-study period (UML diagram)

10.10 Educational activity period element

Term: *educational activity period element (healthcare activity period element)*

Definition: Part of a *educational activity period* during which one *education issue* is specifically addressed

NOTE 1: Several *educational activity period elements* may take place during the course of a *educational activity periods*.

NOTE 2: A *educational activity period elements* is part of only one *educational activity periods* and of only one *episode of learning support*.

EXAMPLE 1: Student feedback session educational activity period element – a portion of an educational activity period could involve providing individual feedback on student work, such as reviewing a draft essay, while the rest of the period might involve lectures or peer discussions.

EXAMPLE 2: Problem-solving exercise educational activity period element – in a mathematics class, one element of an educational activity period could focus on working through a specific problem-solving exercise, such as solving equations, while other elements of the period may focus on theoretical instruction or group exercises.

EXAMPLE 3: Hands-on training educational activity period element – in a vocational training class, an educational activity period element might consist of a hands-on segment where students practice using equipment or tools, like in a nursing skills lab or engineering workshop.

EXAMPLE 4: Test educational activity period element – in a course, one educational activity period element may consist of a short quiz or formative test focused on assessing specific learning outcomes, such as knowledge of vocabulary in a foreign language class.

Table 88 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 98.

Table 88: Associations of *educational activity period element* (tab:88)

Component of		Aggregation of	
1	<i>educational activity period</i>		
1	<i>episode of learning support</i>		

Association from	Association name	Association to
1	<i>education issue</i>	determines 0..* <i>educational activity period element</i>

Figure 98: Educational activity period element (UML diagram)

10.11 Educational appointment

Term: *educational appointment* (healthcare appointment)

Definition: Appointment for a *educational contact*

EXAMPLE 1: Research supervision educational appointment – a meeting between a graduate student and their research supervisor to discuss progress on a thesis or dissertation, refine research methods, or review findings.

EXAMPLE 2: Tutoring educational appointment – a session where a student meets with a tutor for additional help with course content, such as studying for an exam or working through difficult assignments.

Table 89 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 99.

Table 89: Associations of *educational appointment* (tab:89)

Association from	Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational appointment</i>	is scheduled in 0..1 <i>learning plan</i>
1	<i>educational activity period</i>	takes place during 0..1 <i>educational appointment</i>
0..1	<i>educational appointment</i>	is appointment for 1 <i>educational contact</i>

Figure 99: Educational appointment (UML diagram)

10.12 Educational activity delay

Term: *educational activity delay* (*healthcare activity delay*)

Definition: *education related period* during which a *educational activity* is planned but not started

EXAMPLE 1:Exam scheduling delay – a scheduled exam is delayed due to technical issues in an online exam system or conflicts with university-wide scheduling.

EXAMPLE 2:Thesis submission delay – a student’s planned thesis defense is postponed due to delayed feedback from a supervisor or unavailability of examiners.

EXAMPLE 3:Research project delay – a research study planned for a specific semester is delayed due to lack of necessary approvals, funding issues, or participant recruitment challenges.

Table 90 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 100.

Table 90: Associations of *educational activity delay* (tab:90)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
	<i>education related period</i>		<i>educational condition delay</i>
			<i>resource delay</i>
			<i>learner preference delay</i>
Component of		Aggregation of	
1	<i>mandated period of education</i>		

Figure 100: Educational activity delay (UML diagram)

10.13 Educational condition delay

Term: *educational condition delay* (*health condition delay*)

Definition: *educational activity delay* caused by a *education condition*

EXAMPLE 1:Health-related educational delay – a student undergoing medical treatment (e.g., hospitalisation, recovery from surgery) is unable to start or continue a semester as planned.

EXAMPLE 2:Presentation postponed because of a technical issue in the classroom

EXAMPLE 3:Delayed degree completion due to failed courses – a student who fails a required course must retake it in a later semester, postponing graduation.

Table 91 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 101.

Table 91: Associations of *educational condition delay* (tab:91)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>educational activity delay</i>	

Figure 101: Educational condition delay (UML diagram)

10.14 Resource delay

Term: *resource delay* (*resource delay*)

Definition: *educational activity delay* caused by resource constraints where there is no *educational condition delay*

EXAMPLE 1: Educational activity scheduled later than initially planned due to limited availability of teachers (e.g., a waiting list for tutoring sessions)

EXAMPLE 2: Educational activity postponed until necessary financial resources are secured (e.g., delay in purchasing lab equipment for a science class)

Table 92 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 102.

Table 92: Associations of *resource delay* (tab:92)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity delay</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educator</i>	is responsible for	0..* <i>resource delay</i>

Figure 102: Resource delay (UML diagram)

10.15 Learner preference delay

Term: *learner preference delay* (subject of care preference delay)

Definition: *educational activity delay* by the preference of the *learner*, where there is neither a *educational condition delay* nor a *resource delay*

EXAMPLE 1: Examination postponed to accommodate a learner’s seasonal work

EXAMPLE 2: Project presentation delayed to accommodate the learner’s scheduling preference

EXAMPLE 3: Graduation delay by choice – a student who has met graduation requirements extends their academic timeline to take extra courses, complete a minor, or gain additional experience.

Table 93 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 103.

Table 93: Associations of *learner preference delay* (tab:93)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational activity delay</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>learner preference delay</i>	is caused by	1 <i>learner</i>

Figure 103: Learner preference delay (UML diagram)

10.16 Learning process episode

Term: *learning process episode* (*clinical process episode*)

Definition: *education related period* that includes all *educational activity periods* in one *learning process*

EXAMPLE 1:Semester learning episode – the full duration of a semester where a student engages in a set of courses, including lectures, discussions, assignments, exams, and final evaluations.

EXAMPLE 2:Practical training episode – the learning process associated with a training period in a field like engineering or nursing, including workshops, on-site training, skill assessments, and evaluations by instructors.

EXAMPLE 3:Capstone project episode – a student’s journey of completing a capstone project, starting from topic selection, research, development, presentations, and submission, encompassing all the activities that contribute to the final outcome.

EXAMPLE 4:Research project episode – the learning process involved in carrying out a research project, including literature review, hypothesis testing, data analysis, writing the report, and final presentation.

Table 94 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 104.

Table 94: Associations of *learning process episode* (tab:94)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education related period</i>			
Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>educational activity period</i>
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1	<i>learning process episode</i>	is time interval for	1 <i>learning process</i>

Figure 104: Learning process episode (UML diagram)

10.17 Educational condition period

Term: *educational condition period* (health condition period)

Definition: *education related period* during which a *education condition* has been observed

NOTE 1: Observation of a *education condition* may lead to an *episode of learning support*

NOTE 2: *educational condition period* refers only to the observation of the *education condition*, for example, the time interval during which a *learner* has observed difficulty in understanding a subject. The concept *episode of learning support* support refers to the *educational activities*.

EXAMPLE 1: Observed difficulty in understanding course material – a student struggles with understanding a specific subject or concept in a course (e.g., calculus), and the educational condition period refers to the time during which this difficulty is observed by the instructor or learning support staff.

EXAMPLE 2: Difficulty with digital tools – a student faces challenges in using necessary digital tools for online learning. This struggle is observed over a period and can be considered an educational condition period.

Table 95 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 105.

Table 95: Associations of *educational condition period* (tab:95)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education related period</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>observed educational condition</i>	has been observed during	1 <i>educational condition period</i>

Figure 105: Educational condition period (UML diagram)

10.18 Episode of learning support

Term: *episode of learning support* (*episode of care*)

Synonyms: episode of educational support, educational issue related episode

Definition: *education related period* during which *educational activities* are performed to address one *education issue* as identified by one *education professional*

NOTE 1: An *episode of learning support* encompasses all *educational activity period elements* related to the same *education issue*.

NOTE 2: An *episode of learning support* starts with the very first *educational contact* with an *educator* for an *education issue* and ends after the completion of all *educational activities* related to the last *educational contact* with that *educator* for the same *education issue*.

NOTE 3: For practical reasons (e.g., the need to state start and end dates) and also because it relates specifically to an *education issue* defined by a given *education professional*, an *episode of learning support* does not necessarily coincide with an ‘episode of difficulty’ (or of any other kind of *education issue*).

EXAMPLE 1: Online learning assistance – a student struggles with understanding how to navigate an online learning platform. The episode of learning support starts with an initial meeting with the IT helpdesk, continues with training on platform navigation, and concludes once the student is able to effectively use all required tools independently.

EXAMPLE 2: Writing support for thesis completion – a student working on a thesis receives support from a writing tutor to improve structure, grammar, and clarity. The episode of learning support starts with an initial consultation and ends when the student successfully submits the final thesis.

Table 96 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 106.

Table 96: Associations of *episode of learning support* (tab:96)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>education related period</i>		<i>educational approach</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..*	<i>episodes of learning support bundle</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity period element</i>
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>episode of learning support</i>	is centred on	1 <i>education issue</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	manages	0..* <i>episode of learning support</i>

Figure 106: Episode of learning support (UML diagram)

10.19 Educational approach

Term: *educational approach* (*health approach*)

Synonyms: educational strategy, goal-addressing episode of learning support

Definition: *episode of learning support* during which the *educational activities* performed address one specific *educational goal*

EXAMPLE 1: Time management strategy for academic success – if a student is having difficulty meeting deadlines, the educational approach could involve one-on-one coaching sessions, where the goal is to improve time management skills. The activities would focus on teaching prioritization, scheduling, and using tools like planners, with the educational goal being to enhance the student’s ability to submit assignments on time.

EXAMPLE 2: Writing skills development approach – a student struggling with academic writing may receive an educational approach that includes targeted workshops on essay structure, thesis statement creation, and citation formatting. The educational goal is to help the student produce well-structured essays and research papers.

EXAMPLE 3: Research methodology approach – a student preparing to write a thesis or dissertation might receive an educational approach that focuses on mastering research methodologies, including data collection, analysis techniques, and ethical considerations. The educational goal would be to help the student conduct rigorous and ethical research.

Table 97 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 107.

Table 97: Associations of *educational approach* (tab:97)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>episode of learning support</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational approach</i>	addresses	1 <i>educational goal</i>

Figure 107: Educational approach (UML diagram)

10.20 Episodes of learning support bundle

Term: *episodes of learning support bundle* (*episodes of care bundle*)

Synonyms: episodes of educational support bundle, cumulative episode of learning support

Definition: Group of *episode of learning supports* support delineated by an *educational thread*

NOTE: An *episodes of learning support bundle* starts with the very first *educational contact* with an *educator* for an *education issue* considered in an *educational thread* and ends after the completion of all *educational activities* related to the last *educational contact* with any *educator* for an *education issue* encompassed in the same *educational thread*.

EXAMPLE 1: Support for a student with a learning disability – a student with a learning disability receives ongoing support throughout a semester. The episodes of learning support bundle might include specialized tutoring, adaptive technology sessions, counseling, and extended exam time. This bundle starts when the student’s learning disability is identified and continues until all accommodations and educational support activities are completed.

EXAMPLE 2: Support for group work and collaboration – a student struggling with group projects and teamwork might receive support from a tutor or mentor who helps develop collaboration skills, set clear expectations for group roles, and manage conflict. The episodes of learning support bundle begins when the student first seeks help with group collaboration and ends once the group project is completed successfully.

Table 98 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 108.

Table 98: Associations of *episodes of learning support bundle* (tab:98)

Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>episode of learning support</i>
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational thread</i>	delineates	0..1 <i>episodes of learning support bundle</i>

Figure 108: Episodes of learning support bundle (UML diagram)

11 Concepts related to responsibilities

11.1 General

A model showing the associations between the concepts related to responsibility in continuity of education and the other concepts defined in this International Standard is shown in Figure 109. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 109: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to responsibilities

11.2 Educational mandate

Term: *educational mandate (healthcare mandate)*

Synonyms: educational commission

Definition: Mandate (commission) based on a commitment and either an *informed consent* or an authorization by law, defining the rights and obligations of one *educational actor* with regard to their

involvement in *educational processes* performed for a specific *learner*

NOTE 1: A *educational mandate* can be explicit or implicit.

NOTE 2: Relevant information related to *educational mandates* (including demands for care, *informed consents*, *dissents*, *educational commitments*, etc.), is recorded in *educational records* where the information is made available for concerned *educational actors* as *educational concerns*.

NOTE 3: Typically a *educational mandate* is assigned by one *educational actor* to another.

EXAMPLE 1: Mandate for program directors – a program director in charge of a particular academic program receives an educational mandate to oversee the implementation of the program’s curriculum, handle student enrollment, and ensure that the educational objectives are met. The director must work within the boundaries set by the university’s policies and the expectations of both faculty and students.

EXAMPLE 2: Research supervisor’s mandate – a faculty member acting as a research supervisor receives an educational mandate to oversee a student’s thesis or dissertation project. The mandate includes providing guidance, approving research methodologies, and ensuring the ethical conduct of research. The supervisor’s obligations are defined in the context of the student’s educational goals, and the mandate may include certain legal and ethical responsibilities regarding the research process.

Table 99 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 110.

Table 99: Associations of *educational mandate* (tab:99)

Specialization of		Generalization of		
		<i>demand mandate</i>		
		<i>educational period mandate</i>		
		<i>continuity facilitator mandate</i>		
		<i>educational activity mandate</i>		
		<i>mandate to export personal information</i>		
Association from		Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	concerns	1	<i>learner</i>
1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	regulates	1..*	<i>educational process</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	requires	0..1	<i>informed consent</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	requires	0..1	<i>authorization by law</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	is recorded in	0..*	<i>educational record</i>
1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	implies access to	0..*	<i>educational record</i>
1	<i>educational mandate</i>	requires	1	<i>educational commitment</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	derives from	0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	is assigned to	1	<i>educational actor</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	assigns	0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>
0..*	<i>dissent</i>	limits	1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>
0..*	<i>learner desire</i>	influences	0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>

Figure 110: Educational mandate (UML representation)

11.3 Demand mandate

Term: *demand mandate* (*demand mandate*)

Synonyms: demand commission

Definition: *educational mandate* implying the right and obligation to demand *educational activities*

NOTE: A *demand for education* is usually made by a *learner* him/herself, but there are circumstances where the *learner* is not in the position of making a *demand for education*. In that case, another person must make it on their behalf.

EXAMPLE 1: Demand for additional learning materials – a student in a course might issue a demand mandate to request additional learning materials such as supplementary readings, access to specific software tools, or extra practical exercises to better engage with the content.

EXAMPLE 2: Learner with disabilities requesting accommodations – a student with a learning disability might have the demand mandate to request accommodations such as extended exam time, access to assistive technology, or alternative formats for coursework. The student or their representative (e.g., a disability services coordinator) may formalize this demand in alignment with an institution’s policies and regulations.

Table 100 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 111.

Table 100: Associations of *demand mandate* (tab:100)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational mandate</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>demand for education</i>	justifies	0..* <i>demand mandate</i>
0..*	<i>demand mandate</i>	has topic	1..* <i>educational matter</i>
1	<i>demand mandate</i>	gives way to	0..* <i>educational period mandate</i>
1	<i>demand mandate</i>	permits	0..* <i>continuity facilitator mandate</i>
1	<i>demand mandate</i>	permits	0..* <i>mandate to export personal information</i>

Figure 111: Demand mandate (UML representation)

11.4 Educational period mandate

Term: *educational period mandate* (*care period mandate*)

Definition: *educational mandate* commissioning a *mandated period of education*

NOTE: A *educational period mandate* may be an agreement between the *learner* and a *educator* to provide specified *educational services* in a *mandated period of education*.

EXAMPLE 1: Enrollment agreement - a formal contract between a student and a university confirming participation in an academic program University admission acceptance letter, tuition agreement

EXAMPLE 2: Scholarship or grant agreement A mandate specifying academic performance requirements for receiving financial aid Government-funded scholarship conditions, private grant agreements

EXAMPLE 3: A contractual agreement between a student, university, and host organization for practical learning.

EXAMPLE 4: Thesis or dissertation supervision agreement. An agreement outlining the supervision structure, deadlines, and research expectations PhD dissertation supervision plan.

EXAMPLE 5: Exchange program or study abroad agreement - a formal arrangement between institutions for a student's temporary education abroad Erasmus+ study abroad contract, university partnership agreement.

Table 101 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 112.

Table 101: Associations of *educational period mandate* (tab:101)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational mandate</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>educational period mandate</i>	has topic	1..* <i>educational matter</i>
1..*	<i>educational period mandate</i>	authorizes	0..* <i>education provider activity</i>
1	<i>demand mandate</i>	gives way to	0..* <i>educational period mandate</i>
0..1	<i>demand for education</i>	triggers	0..1 <i>educational period mandate</i>
1	<i>educational period mandate</i>	commissions	1..* <i>educational service</i>
1	<i>educational period mandate</i>	commissions	1 <i>mandated period of education</i>
0..*	<i>continuity facilitator mandate</i>	applies to	1..* <i>educational period mandate</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	is able to be assigned	1..* <i>educational period mandate</i>

Figure 112: Educational period mandate (UML representation)

11.5 Educational activity mandate

Term: *educational activity mandate* (*healthcare activity mandate*)

Synonyms: educational activity commission

Definition: *educational mandate* assigning the right and obligation to perform specific *educational activities*

EXAMPLE 1: Teaching assignment mandate assigns an educator to conduct specific courses or training sessions. University professor assigned to teach the programming study course.

EXAMPLE 2: Student research mandate authorizes a learner to conduct specific research under supervision

Master’s thesis approval, PhD dissertation research.

EXAMPLE 3: Internship supervision mandate assigns an academic supervisor to oversee student internships.

EXAMPLE 4: Curriculum development mandate assigns educators to develop new course materials.

EXAMPLE 5: Accredited training provider mandate authorizes an institution to deliver certified training programs. University certified as an official training center.

EXAMPLE 6: Third-party educational activity mandate delegates educational responsibilities to external entities Private company mandated to provide vocational training.

Table 102 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 113.

Table 102: Associations of *educational activity mandate* (tab:102)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational mandate</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>education provider activity</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity mandate</i>
0..*	<i>educational third party activity</i>	1..*	<i>educational activity mandate</i>

Figure 113: Educational activity mandate (UML representation)

11.6 Continuity facilitator mandate

Term: *continuity facilitator mandate* (*continuity facilitator mandate*)

Synonyms: continuity facilitator commission

Definition: *educational mandate* assigning the right and obligation to monitor and coordinate the delivery *educational activities* described in those *educational period mandates* related to *educational matters* linked

by specific *educational threads*

NOTE 1: Beyond solely assuming the function described above, a continuity facilitator may also assume the role of a lead and/or coordinator of *educational activities* delivered to the *learners*.

NOTE 2: A continuity facilitation can be fulfilled only if the involved *educational actors* have the information needed to perform their tasks in *educational activities*

NOTE 3: For continuity of care the *continuity facilitator mandates* for complete *learning processes* are of special importance from the *learners* perspective.

EXAMPLE 1:A mandate assigned to a coordinating teacher, academic advisor, program director, or key educational worker to coordinate educational activities.

EXAMPLE 2:Work-based learning programs for students participating in cooperative education (co-op) or internships - a continuity facilitator mandate might involve coordinating the academic and professional components of the program. The facilitator would ensure that the students' workplace experiences are linked with their academic coursework, offering support and feedback to integrate both aspects into a cohesive learning process.

EXAMPLE 3:Student progress monitoring - a continuity facilitator mandate might be assigned to a faculty advisor or program director who monitors the progress of a student throughout their educational journey. This could include ensuring that the student's courses, internships, and research projects are coordinated so that all components work together to achieve the student's career and academic goals.

Table 103 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 114.

Table 103: Associations of *continuity facilitator mandate* (tab:103)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational mandate</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>continuity facilitator mandate</i>	has topic	0..* <i>educational thread</i>
1	<i>demand mandate</i>	permits	0..* <i>continuity facilitator mandate</i>
0..*	<i>continuity facilitator mandate</i>	applies to	1..* <i>educational period mandate</i>

Figure 114: Continuity facilitator mandate (UML representation)

11.7 Mandate to export personal information

Term: *mandate to export personal information* (*mandate to export personal information*)

Synonyms: commission to export personal information

Definition: *educational mandate* implying the right to communicate *educational record extracts*

EXAMPLE: Request for academic record transfer - a student moving to another university may request a mandate to export personal information from their current institution to their new one. This could involve sending academic transcripts, grades, and other educational records to the new academic advisor or educational institution, facilitating the student's transfer or enrollment process.

Table 104 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 115.

Table 104: Associations of *mandate to export personal information* (tab:104)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational mandate</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>mandate to export personal information</i>	has topic	1..* <i>educational matter</i>
1..*	<i>mandate to export personal information</i>	implies the right to communicate	1..* <i>educational record extract</i>
1	<i>demand mandate</i>	permits	0..* <i>mandate to export personal information</i>

Figure 115: Mandate to export personal information (UML representation)

11.8 Informed consent

Term: *informed consent* (*informed consent*)

Definition: Permission to perform *educational activities*, voluntarily given by a *learner* having consent competence, or by a *learner proxy*, after having been informed about the purpose and the possible results of the *educational activities*

EXAMPLE 1: Research study participation - a university professor conducting research on the effectiveness of online learning strategies asks students to participate in the study. Before any data is collected, the professor provides the students with an informed consent form that explains the study's purpose, methodology, the type of data being collected, how their responses will be used, and any potential risks or benefits. Students must voluntarily sign the form before taking part.

EXAMPLE 2: Educational data usage - in an education-based research project, a university collects data on student performance or behavior to improve teaching methods. Before collecting any data, the students are informed about how their academic records will be used, stored, and shared. They are then asked to provide informed consent before their information is included in the study.

EXAMPLE 3: Survey participation for course feedback - at the end of a semester, students are asked to complete a course evaluation survey. The students are informed about how their feedback will be used to improve the course and teaching methods. By voluntarily completing the survey, they provide informed consent, understanding that their responses will be analysed anonymously and incorporated into course development.

Table 105 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 116.

Table 105: Associations of *informed consent* (tab:105)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>informed consent</i>	requires	1	<i>consent competence</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	gives	0..*	<i>informed consent</i>
0..1	<i>learner proxy</i>	gives	0..*	<i>informed consent</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	requires	0..1	<i>informed consent</i>

Figure 116: Informed consent (UML representation)

11.9 Dissent

Term: *dissent* (*dissent*)

Definition: Refusal to permit specific *educational activities* to be performed

EXAMPLE 1: Refusal to participate in research studies - a university student is asked to participate in a study that involves gathering data from participants to evaluate a new teaching method. The student, after reviewing the study's consent form, dissents from participating, indicating that they do not wish to be part of the research. As a result, the student's decision is respected, and they are excluded from the study.

EXAMPLE 2: Refusal to consent to recording in class - during a university lecture, the professor mentions that the lecture will be recorded for use in an online course resource. Some students may dissent by not giving their permission for their images or voices to be recorded, and the university may accommodate their

preferences by not including them in the recordings.

Table 106 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 117.

Table 106: Associations of *dissent* (tab:106)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>dissent</i>	requires	1	<i>consent competence</i>
0..*	<i>dissent</i>	limits	1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	states	0..*	<i>dissent</i>
0..1	<i>learner proxy</i>	states	0..*	<i>dissent</i>

Figure 117: Dissent (UML representation)

11.10 Consent competence

Term: *consent competence* (*consent competence*)

Definition: Capability of the *learner* and/or the *learner proxy* to give *informed consent* or *dissent*

EXAMPLE 1: Ability to understand informed consent in research - a graduate student is invited to participate in a university-led research study. The student must demonstrate consent competence by understanding the research purpose, risks, and benefits outlined in the consent form. The student must be able to ask questions and voluntarily agree to participate.

EXAMPLE 2: Competence to refuse participation in research or class activities - a student may be asked to sign a consent form for a study that involves educational activities such as video recording. If the student has consent competence, they can clearly understand their right to refuse participation in the study (*dissent*) and express their decision to opt out.

EXAMPLE 3: Informed consent in medical or healthcare programs - a medical student might be involved in a clinical practicum where the patient's consent is required for certain procedures. The student must demonstrate consent competence by understanding the ethical guidelines, the patient's rights, and how to seek consent for medical activities.

Table 107 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 118.

Table 107: Associations of *consent competence* (tab:107)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>informed consent</i>	requires	1	<i>consent competence</i>
0..*	<i>dissent</i>	requires	1	<i>consent competence</i>
0..*	<i>learner proxy</i>	has	1	<i>consent competence</i>
0..1	<i>learner</i>	has	0..1	<i>consent competence</i>

Figure 118: Consent competence (UML representation)

11.11 Authorization by law

Term: *authorization by law* (*authorization by law*)

Definition: Provision in legislation that in certain circumstances may overrule the need for *informed consent*

EXAMPLE:Data sharing under legal requirements: universities may be required by law to share student data with government bodies or law enforcement under specific circumstances, such as compliance with financial aid regulations or investigations. This legal obligation allows the sharing of information without the need for individual consent.

Table 108 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 119.

Table 108: Associations of *authorization by law* (tab:108)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	requires	0..1	<i>authorization by law</i>

Figure 119: Authorization by law (UML representation)

11.12 Educational commitment

Term: *educational commitment* (*healthcare commitment*)

Definition: Acceptance of a *educational mandate* by the *educational actor* to whom it is assigned

NOTE: The *educational commitment* is the promise by the *educational actor* to perform *educational activities*. This also means that the *educator* accepts and confirms the pending *educational mandate* issued through the proposed education plan. It is only once the *educational commitment* has been stated that an effective *educational mandate* exists and will be the legal framework for all *educational activities* of the subsequent *educational process*.

EXAMPLE: University accepting students to the program, school accepting a pupil, tutoring services signing the contract to the student, private teacher signing the contract to the student

Table 109 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 120.

Table 109: Associations of *educational commitment* (tab:109)

Association from	Association name	Association to
0..1 <i>educational commitment</i>	relates to the provision of	1..* <i>educational activity</i>
1 <i>educational mandate</i>	requires	1 <i>educational commitment</i>
1 <i>educator</i>	states	1..* <i>educational commitment</i>
0..1 <i>referral</i>	asks for	1 <i>educational commitment</i>

Figure 120: Educational commitment (UML representation)

11.13 Learner desire

Term: *learner desire* (*subject of care desire*)

Definition: Desire expressed by the *learner* or the *learner proxy* regarding the performance of certain *educational activity*

EXAMPLE: A student expressing a desire to focus on specific subjects, such as advanced mathematics or creative writing. A learner wishing to participate in extracurricular activities, such as joining a debate club or sports team.

Table 110 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 121.

Table 110: Associations of *learner desire* (tab:110)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..1	<i>learner</i>	expresses	0..*	<i>learner desire</i>
0..1	<i>learner proxy</i>	expresses	0..*	<i>learner desire</i>
0..*	<i>learner desire</i>	influences	0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>
0..*	<i>learner desire</i>	is considered during	1..*	<i>educational needs assessment</i>
0..*	<i>learner desire</i>	is recorded in	0..*	<i>educational record</i>

Figure 121: Learner desire (UML representation)

11.14 Demand for education

Term: *demand for education* (*demand for care*)

Definition: Demand for *education provider activities* expressed by a *educational actor*

NOTE 1: A *demand for education* may be expressed either by the *learner* or on their behalf.

NOTE 2: A *educator* may accept or decline a *demand for education*.

EXAMPLE 1: Enrollment in a new course or program - a student expressing interest in enrolling in a particular course or academic program for the upcoming semester is making a demand for education. The demand is directed at the educational provider to deliver the requested courses or programs, assuming they are available.

EXAMPLE 2: Student request for access to online learning resources - a student who is unable to attend classes in person due to unforeseen circumstances (e.g., illness, travel) may request access to online resources, lectures, or recorded sessions. This would be a demand for education to facilitate their continued learning remotely.

Table 111 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 122.

Table 111: Associations of *demand for education* (tab:111)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>referral</i>	
		<i>request</i>	
		<i>demand for initial contact</i>	
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>demand for education</i>	0..*	<i>demand mandate</i>
0..1	<i>demand for education</i>	1..*	<i>education provider activity</i>
0..*	<i>demand for education</i>	1..*	<i>educational matter</i>
1	<i>reason for demand for education</i>	0..*	<i>demand for education</i>
1..*	<i>educational actor</i>	0..*	<i>demand for education</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	1..*	<i>demand for education</i>
1	<i>educator</i>	1..*	<i>demand for education</i>
0..*	<i>education professional</i>	0..*	<i>demand for education</i>
0..1	<i>demand for education</i>	0..1	<i>educational period mandate</i>

Figure 122: Demand for education (UML representation)

11.15 Demand for initial contact

Term: *demand for initial contact* (*demand for initial contact*)

Definition: First *demand for education* concerning one or more specific *education issues* to be assessed by a *educator*

EXAMPLE 1: First meeting with a tutor - a student struggling with a particular subject might request the first meeting with a tutor or teaching assistant to discuss their difficulties. This request is a demand for initial contact, where the educator can assess the student's specific needs and plan the support accordingly.

EXAMPLE 2: Request for guidance on research project - a graduate student may approach their professor or mentor for an initial meeting to discuss a potential research project. This first request for contact is a demand for initial contact, during which the professor will assess the student's research ideas and provide direction on how to proceed.

Table 112 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 123.

Table 112: Associations of *demand for initial contact* (tab:112)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>demand for education</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..1 <i>demand for initial contact</i>	results in	0..1	<i>educational initial contact</i>

Figure 123: Demand for initial contact (UML representation)

11.16 Referral

Term: *referral* (*referral*)

Definition: *demand for education* where a *education professional* asks a *educator* to state a *educational commitment* for a *educational period mandate*

NOTE: An accepted *referral* transfers the continuity responsibility for the *education issues* specified in the *referral*.

EXAMPLE 1: A biology professor refers a student interested in genetic research to a faculty member who conducts research in genetics.

EXAMPLE 2: A student who cannot afford textbooks may be referred to the financial aid office for potential assistance with book subsidies or grants.

Table 113 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 124.

Table 113: Associations of *referral* (tab:113)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>demand for education</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..1	<i>referral</i>	initiates	0..1 <i>educational contact</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	issues	0..* <i>referral</i>
0..1	<i>referral</i>	asks for	1 <i>educational commitment</i>

Figure 124: Referral (UML representation)

11.17 Request

Term: *request* (*request*)

Synonyms: order, educational provider activity request

Definition: *demand for education* where a *education professional* asks a *educator* to perform one or more *education provider activities*

NOTE 1: A *request* is put forward by a *education professional* within a *educational process*.

NOTE 2: The responsibility for the requested *education provider activities* is held by the performer but they will be performed under the *educational period mandate* of the requester.

NOTE 3: A *educator* may accept or decline a *request* (order) to perform *educational activities*.

EXAMPLE 1: Lecturer requests the IT team to install MATLAB on all university lab computers before the start of the computational physics course.

EXAMPLE 2: Student requests the department chair for an override to enrol in the course of advanced economics despite not having taken the prerequisite course."

Table 114 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 125.

Table 114: Associations of *request* (tab:114)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>demand for education</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1	<i>education professional</i>	issues	0..* <i>request</i>

Figure 125: Request (UML representation)

11.18 Reason for demand for education

Term: *reason for demand for education* (*reason for demand for care*)

Definition: *learner* or a *learner proxy*'s perception of *educational needs* motivating a *demand for education*.

NOTE: There are needs for both direct (healthcare investigating and *educational instruction*) and indirect (*educational assessments, educational planning, educational evaluation, etc.*) *educational activities*.

EXAMPLE 1:A PhD student is struggling with their thesis methodology and requests guidance from a research supervisor.

EXAMPLE 2:A student is struggling with calculus and requests extra tutoring sessions (one-on-one tutoring sessions).

Table 115 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 126.

Table 115: Associations of *reason for demand for education* (tab:115)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
1	<i>reason for demand for education</i>	motivates	0..*	<i>demand for education</i>
0..*	<i>educational need</i>	is background for	0..*	<i>reason for demand for education</i>
0..*	<i>reason for demand for education</i>	is expressed by	0..1	<i>learner</i>
0..*	<i>reason for demand for education</i>	is expressed by	0..*	<i>learner proxy</i>

Figure 126: Reason for demand for education (UML representation)

12 Concepts related to information management

12.1 General

A model showing the associations between the concepts related to *educational information* management in *continuity of education* and the other concepts defined in this International Standard is shown in Figure 127. For further details about the diagram notation, please refer to 1.7 in the Introduction.

Figure 127: Comprehensive UML diagram of concepts related to information management

12.2 Educational record

Term: *educational record* (health record)

Definition: *data repository* regarding the education and educational progress of a *learner*

NOTE 1: The term electronic *educational record* may be used for an *educational record* where all information is stored on electronic media. However, this concept is not formally defined in this International Standard.

NOTE 2: An *educational record* may include, for example, academic records, attendance records, and extracurricular activity records.

EXAMPLE 1: A student requests their educational record for verification of their bachelor's degree before applying for jobs.

EXAMPLE 2: Student transcript – contains course history, grades, etc.

EXAMPLE 3: Attendance records – logs of class attendance and participation.

Table 116 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 128.

Table 116: Associations of *educational record* (tab:116)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>data repository</i>		<i>professional educational record</i>	
		<i>personal educational record</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>educational record component</i>
Association from		Association name	Association to
1..*	<i>educational record</i>	concerns	1 <i>learner</i>
0..*	<i>educational record</i>	is accessed during	1..* <i>educational activity period</i>
0..*	<i>educational record</i>	is accessed during	1..* <i>educational activity</i>
0..*	<i>educational record</i>	is stored on	1..* <i>medium</i>
1..*	<i>educational activity</i>	is recorded in	0..* <i>educational record</i>
0..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	is recorded in	0..* <i>educational record</i>
1..*	<i>educational mandate</i>	implies access to	0..* <i>educational record</i>
0..*	<i>educational record extract</i>	is extracted from	1 <i>educational record</i>
0..*	<i>non-ratified educational information</i>	is recorded in	0..* <i>educational record</i>
1..*	<i>educational documenting</i>	maintains	1..* <i>educational record</i>
1..*	<i>educational process</i>	is documented in	0..* <i>educational record</i>
0..*	<i>learning plan</i>	is recorded in	0..* <i>educational record</i>
0..*	<i>learner desire</i>	is recorded in	0..* <i>educational record</i>

Figure 128: Educational record (UML diagram)

12.3 Professional educational record

Term: *professional educational record* (*professional health record*)

Definition: *educational record* held under the responsibility of one *educator* and maintained by one or several *education professionals*

NOTE: The responsible *educator* may allow the *learner* to access and/or offer contributions to the professional *professional educational record*.

EXAMPLE 1: Student progress notes - professors or academic advisors maintain records of their interactions with students, which may include feedback on assignments, performance during office hours, and notes on areas for improvement. Students may have access to these records to view their progress and provide additional input.

EXAMPLE 2: Research project documentation - in academic settings where students engage in research, the supervising faculty member may maintain a professional educational record that tracks the student's contributions, data, and progress toward project goals. The student may have access to this record to ensure alignment with academic objectives.

EXAMPLE 3: Evaluation and feedback records - a faculty member may keep detailed records of feedback and evaluations provided to students on exams, presentations, or coursework. These records may be shared with the student to help them understand areas for improvement and their academic growth over time.

Table 117 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 129.

Table 117: Associations of *professional educational record* (tab:117)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational record</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educator</i>	is responsible for	0..* <i>professional educational record</i>
1..*	<i>education professional</i>	maintains	0..* <i>professional educational record</i>
1..*	<i>mandated period of education</i>	is documented in	1..* <i>professional educational record</i>
0..*	<i>educational information for import</i>	is imported into	1 <i>professional educational record</i>

Figure 129: Professional educational record (UML diagram)

12.4 Personal educational record

Term: *personal educational record* (*personal health record*)

Definition: *educational record* held and maintained by the *learner* or a *learner proxy*

NOTE: A *learner* may allow any *educational actor* to access and/or offer contributions to the *personal educational record*.

EXAMPLE 1: Student-generated feedback on courses - while educators often maintain records of feedback provided to students, students may also keep records of their own feedback on courses, teaching methods, or educational experiences. This feedback can be stored in a personal educational record and may be used for future course selection or academic planning.

EXAMPLE 2: A student keeps track of completed courses. A student logs online courses, independent research. A record of completed certifications, workshops, and acquired competencies.

EXAMPLE 3: Stored feedback from professors, mentors, and peers on assignments and projects. A student saves professor comments on essays and project evaluations.

EXAMPLE 4: Personal learning objectives and structured learning plans. A student outlines career goals and maps required courses to achieve them.

EXAMPLE 5: Documentation of internships, assistantships, and job-related learning. A student includes

internship reports and employer evaluations.

Table 118 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 130.

Table 118: Associations of *personal educational record* (tab:118)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational record</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..1	<i>learner</i>	maintains	0..* <i>personal educational record</i>
0..*	<i>learner proxy</i>	maintains	0..* <i>personal educational record</i>

Figure 130: Personal educational record (UML diagram)

12.5 Educational record component

Term: *educational record component* (*health record component*)

Definition: Part of a *educational record* that is identifiable for the purposes of referencing and revision

NOTE 1: This International Standard defines one *educational record component* specialization, the *electronic educational record component*. However, as the content of a *educational record* is not limited to information in electronic format, the content of *educational record components* may be in formats other than electronic.

NOTE 2: A *educational record component* may itself result from an aggregation of multiple *educational record components*.

EXAMPLE 1: Transcripts – official records of courses completed, grades achieved, and credits earned. Assessments results – test scores, assignments, and evaluations that measure learner performance. Assessment results are referenced by instructors, learners, and academic advisors to evaluate progress and outcomes.

EXAMPLE 2: Learning portfolios – collections of work showcasing skills, competencies, and progress over time.

EXAMPLE 3: Attendance records – logs of student participation in classes or learning activities.

EXAMPLE 4: Certifications and credentials – evidence of completion of courses, training, or qualifications.

EXAMPLE 5: Teacher feedback and reports – qualitative evaluations and comments on student performance.

EXAMPLE 6: Competency records – documentation of acquired skills, knowledge, and competencies.

Extracurricular Activities and achievements – Participation in clubs, sports, community service, and

leadership roles.

EXAMPLE 7: Learning analytics and progress tracking – data-driven insights into student engagement, learning patterns, and development. Self-reflections and student journals – learner-generated reflections on personal growth and educational experiences.

EXAMPLE 8: Collaboration and peer evaluations – records of group projects, teamwork contributions, and peer assessments.

Table 119 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 131.

Table 119: Associations of *educational record component* (tab:119)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>electronic educational record component</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..*	<i>educational record</i>	0..*	<i>educational record component</i>
0..*	<i>educational record extract</i>		
0..*	<i>educational record component</i>		
0..*	<i>certificate related to an educational matter</i>		
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..1	<i>educational matter</i>	is used as label for	0..* <i>educational record component</i>

Figure 131: Educational record component (UML diagram)

12.6 Electronic educational record component

Term: *electronic educational record component* (*electronic health record component*)

Definition: *educational record component* which only includes information in electronic format

EXAMPLE 1: E-transcripts, LMS-stored grades, digital certificates. University databases, student portals, blockchain diplomas. Linked with LMS, SIS, or e-learning platforms. Blockchain-based credentials, encrypted grade reports. Continuous grade updates, automated attendance tracking

EXAMPLE 2: Academic records - digital transcripts, diplomas, degree audits. Assessments and feedback online exam results, automated grading reports.

EXAMPLE 3: Course and learning activities - LMS-stored coursework, online discussion logs extracurricular and professional development e-portfolios, digital internship reports

EXAMPLE 4: Certifications and competencies MOOC certificates, digital badges (Coursera, edX, LinkedIn Learning).

EXAMPLE 5: Research and publications - E-theses, online journal articles, ORCID profiles

EXAMPLE 6: Administrative and financial records E-enrollment verification, digital tuition invoices

EXAMPLE 7: Digital storage - the component exists solely in a digital format, which can be stored in cloud-based systems, databases, or learning management systems (LMS). This allows for easy access, retrieval, and sharing of the component as needed.

Table 120 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 132.

Table 120: Associations of *electronic educational record component* (tab:120)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational record component</i>			
Component of		Aggregation of	
0..*	<i>electronic educational record extract</i>		
Association from	Association name	Association to	

Figure 132: Electronic educational record component (UML diagram)

12.7 Sharable educational data repository

Term: *sharable educational data repository* (*sharable data repository*)

Definition: *data repository* containing exclusively *electronic educational record extracts*, accessible for duly authorized *educational actors* independent of their organizational affiliation and placed under the custody of a *educational actor*

NOTE: A *sharable educational data repository* has to be placed under the custody of a *educational actor* in order to ensure and maintain its consistency.

EXAMPLE 1: Student academic records, course completion data. Secure login via university credentials, federated authentication Inter-Institutional. Exchange programs, research collaborations. University IT department, national academic agency. Automated updates, version control mechanisms

EXAMPLE 2: Academic credentials and records Europass, National Student Clearinghouse (USA), EBSI (EU Blockchain for Education)

EXAMPLE 3: Research and scholarly data ORCID, ResearchGate, Google scholar profiles.

EXAMPLE 4: Learning outcomes and Certifications Credly, Open Badges, Digital Diplomas.

EXAMPLE 5: Course and curriculum data. Cross-institutional LMS integrations.

EXAMPLE 6: Online educational platforms or learning management systems (LMS) - Educational platforms like Coursera or Moodle, which work with multiple universities or organizations, could operate sharable data repositories that store educational progress, certification records, and user performance data. These records are available for authorized instructors, administrators, and future employers who require access to the learner's educational achievements.

Table 121 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 133.

Table 121: Associations of *sharable educational data repository* (tab:121)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>data repository</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
1	<i>educational actor</i>	is responsible for	0..* <i>sharable educational data repository</i>
1..*	<i>electronic educational record extract</i>	is imported into	0..* <i>sharable educational data repository</i>
0..*	<i>electronic educational record extract</i>	is extracted from	0..* <i>sharable educational data repository</i>

Figure 133: Sharable educational data repository (UML diagram)

12.8 Summarized educational information repository

Term: *summarized educational information repository* (*summarized healthcare information repository*)

Synonyms: learner summary repository

Definition: *data repository* containing summarized information for educational coordination and the continuity of learning

EXAMPLE 1:Learner progress reports, skill summaries, course highlights. Advising, transfer student support, study abroad programs. Bridging programs, microcredential tracking, lifelong learning pathways. Academic advisors, faculty, institutional administrators.

EXAMPLE 2:University student information Systems (SIS) – platforms like Moodle store summarized learner progress.

EXAMPLE 3:Learning analytics dashboards – AI-powered dashboards that provide student progress insights to educators.

EXAMPLE 4:Cross-institutional learning summaries – used in exchange programs (e.g., Erasmus+) to track student progress.

EXAMPLE 5:Lifelong learning profiles – digital records that consolidate formal education, professional development, and self-learning activities.

Table 122 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 134.

Table 122: Associations of *summarized educational information repository* (tab:122)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>sharable educational data repository</i>			
Component of		Aggregation of	
		0..*	<i>electronic learner summary</i>

Figure 134: Summarized educational information repository (UML diagram)

12.9 Educational record extract

Term: *educational record extract* (*health record extract*)

Definition: Part or all of a *educational record* extracted for the purpose of communication

EXAMPLE 1:A student applies for a Master’s program and submits an official transcript to the admissions office.

EXAMPLE 2:Degree verification letter - confirmation of degree completion. A graduate provides an employer with a document confirming their awarded degree.

EXAMPLE 3:Enrollment certificate proof of current student status. A student needs an enrollment certificate to apply for a student visa.

EXAMPLE 4:Course completion certificate. Proof of successful completion of a course/module. A student who completed an online micro-credential program submits a certificate for credit transfer.

EXAMPLE 5:Learning plan extract. Sharing selected elements of a learning plan. A student shares their learning objectives with an academic advisor for guidance.

EXAMPLE 6:Recommendation letter - academic reference from a professor. A student requests a professor to provide a recommendation letter for a scholarship application.

EXAMPLE 7:Internship or practical training report. Summary of learning outcomes from an internship. A student submits an internship report to fulfill course requirements.

EXAMPLE 8:Educational achievement report. Summary of academic performance and skills. A student compiles key achievements for a portfolio submission.

EXAMPLE 9:Assessment and feedback extract compilation of performance evaluations. A student includes professor feedback in their application for a competitive research program.

Table 123 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 135.

Table 123: Associations of *educational record extract* (tab:123)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
		<i>educational report</i>	
		<i>electronic educational record extract</i>	
		<i>educational concern</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>educational record component</i>
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational record extract</i>	is extracted from	1 <i>educational record</i>
1..*	<i>mandate to export personal information</i>	implies the right to communicate	1..* <i>educational record extract</i>
0..1	<i>educational matter</i>	is used as label for	0..* <i>educational record extract</i>
0..*	<i>educational information request</i>	is topic for	0..* <i>educational record extract</i>

Figure 135: Educational record extract (UML diagram)

12.10 Electronic educational record extract

Term: *electronic educational record extract* (*electronic health record extract*)

Definition: *educational record extract* consisting solely of *electronic educational record components*

EXAMPLE 1: Digital transcript official record of academic history. A student requests a digitally signed transcript.

EXAMPLE 2: Proof of active student status. A student downloads an enrollment certificate from the university portal for visa renewal.

EXAMPLE 3: Automated course completion. Certificate instant verification of course completion. A student completes an online micro-course and receives a digital completion certificate.

EXAMPLE 4: Assessment and feedback report. Digital summary of academic progress. A student downloads professor feedback from the learning management system (LMS).

Table 124 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 136.

Table 124: Associations of *electronic educational record extract* (tab:124)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational record extract</i>		<i>electronic learner summary</i>	
Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>electronic educational record component</i>
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..* <i>electronic educational record extract</i>	is imported into	0..*	<i>sharable educational data repository</i>
0..* <i>electronic educational record extract</i>	is extracted from	0..*	<i>sharable educational data repository</i>

Figure 136: Electronic educational record extract (UML diagram)

12.11 Electronic learner summary

Term: *electronic learner summary* (*electronic patient summary*)

Definition: *electronic educational record extract* containing essential *educational information* intended

for specific uses

EXAMPLE 1: Student profile summary - overview of learning achievements, competency-based summary, academic summary, continuity learning record, an electronic learner summary providing an educational professional with essential information needed for coordinated educational support.

EXAMPLE 2: Exchange student summary - essential academic details for study abroad. A university compiles a student's learning summary for an Erasmus+ exchange program.

Table 125 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 137.

Table 125: Associations of *electronic learner summary* (tab:125)

Specialization of		Generalization of
<i>electronic educational record extract</i>		
Component of		Aggregation of
0..*	<i>summarized educational information repository</i>	

Figure 137: Electronic learner summary (UML diagram)

12.12 Educational report

Term: *educational report (clinical report)*

Definition: *educational record extract* conveying specifically focused educational information to fulfil current information needs of the recipient

EXAMPLE: Progress report, assessment report

EXAMPLE 1: Progress report, assessment report, tracks academic performance over a period.

EXAMPLE 2: Learning Outcome Report Assesses acquired competencies. A student presents this report to validate learning outcomes for a micro-credential.

EXAMPLE 3: Exchange program report summarizes academic achievements for mobility programs. A student submits this to an international partner university before an exchange semester.

EXAMPLE 4: Internship or practical training report documents learning experiences in a work setting. A student submits a report detailing skills gained during an internship.

Table 126 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 138.

Table 126: Associations of *educational report* (tab:126)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational record extract</i>		<i>completion report</i>	
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational report</i>	0..*	<i>non-ratified educational information</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	0..*	<i>educational report</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	0..*	<i>educational report</i>

Figure 138: Educational report (UML diagram)

12.13 Completion report

Term: *completion report (discharge report)*

Definition: *educational report* concerning a completed, *mandated period of education*

EXAMPLE 1: Course completion report confirms successful completion of a single course. A student needs proof of course completion for transfer credits.

EXAMPLE 2: Degree completion report (graduation letter) verifies fulfillment of all program requirements. A graduating student submits this to the university to receive their diploma.

EXAMPLE 3: Internship completion report certifies the completion of practical training. A student submits this report for internship credit validation.

EXAMPLE 4: Exchange program completion report confirms participation and academic achievements in an exchange program. A student returning from Erasmus submits this to their home university.

EXAMPLE 5: Professional certification completion report documents successful completion of a specialized training program.

Table 127 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 139.

Table 127: Associations of *completion report* (tab:127)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational report</i>		<i>completion summary</i>	
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1..*	<i>completion report</i>	concerns	1 <i>mandated period of education</i>

Figure 139: Completion report (UML diagram)

12.14 Completion summary

Term: *completion summary* (*discharge summary*)

Definition: *completion report* summarizing a *mandated period of education*

NOTE 1: A *completion summary* may be provided to the *learner*.

NOTE 2: One *mandated period of education* may be immediately followed by another; the next *educator* will then be a main recipient of the *completion summary*.

NOTE 3: *completion summaries* are often meant to be processed to categorize educational achievements according to a statistically designed classification (such as grade levels or other systems), usually for academic tracking or reporting purposes.

EXAMPLE 1: Degree completion summary summarizes the student's academic journey in a completed degree program. A university sends this to accreditation bodies or employers.

EXAMPLE 2: Semester completion summary documents a student's achievements during a specific semester. Used for student progress tracking and academic advising.

EXAMPLE 3: Course completion summary. Summarizes a student's performance in a particular course. A student transfers credits to another institution.

EXAMPLE 4: Exchange program summary reports learning outcomes from an international academic exchange. Helps home universities recognize coursework from abroad.

EXAMPLE 5: Internship or practicum summary summarizes key skills and outcomes from an internship or practicum. Submitted as part of professional training records.

Table 128 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 140.

Table 128: Associations of *completion summary* (tab:128)

Specialization of	Generalization of
<i>completion report</i>	

Figure 140: Completion summary (UML diagram)

12.15 Non-ratified educational information

Term: *non-ratified educational information* (*non-ratified healthcare information*)

Definition: *educational information* the relevance of which has not been assessed and explicitly stated as valid by an *education professional*

NOTE 1: *educational information* that has been received and is proposed for incorporation in a *professional educational record* may not yet have been reviewed for validity or context by the *education professional*, and as such its accuracy may remain arguable.

NOTE 2: Regardless of the technical process meant practically, *educational information* cannot be ‘inserted’ into a *professional educational record* unless ratified by an *education professional*. They are held in secure temporary storage until a decision is made regarding their insertion or rejection. An exception to this would be when an *education professional* would directly import *educational information* from a *sharable educational data repository* into the local *educational record* they hold. In the case where this import resulted from a request to the *educational actor* in the custody of whom the *sharable educational data repository* is placed, that *educational information* would then need validation.

EXAMPLE 1:Provisional grades - the grades that have been submitted but not yet officially recorded. A professor enters tentative grades, pending final review.

EXAMPLE 2:Unverified transfer credits - the credits from another institution awaiting evaluation. A student transfers from another university, but the registrar must assess course equivalencies.

EXAMPLE 3:Self-reported achievements - information provided by students but not yet checked. A student submits certifications for additional credits, but they need verification.

EXAMPLE 4:Unapproved research contributions - academic work submitted for record inclusion but not yet validated. A student submits research output for inclusion in their academic transcript, but faculty review is pending.

EXAMPLE 5:Pending thesis or dissertation status. A thesis submission awaiting approval. A PhD candidate’s dissertation is submitted but not yet ratified by the review committee.

Table 129 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 141.

Table 129: Associations of *non-ratified educational information* (tab:129)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational information</i>			
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>non-ratified educational information</i>	is recorded in	0..* <i>educational record</i>
0..*	<i>non-ratified educational information</i>	becomes	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
0..*	<i>educational report</i>	is received as	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
0..*	<i>self-learning activity</i>	generates	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
0..*	<i>educational third party activity</i>	generates	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
0..*	<i>automated education</i>	results in	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>

Figure 141: Non-ratified educational information (UML diagram)

12.16 Educational information for import

Term: *educational information for import* (*healthcare information for import*)

Definition: *educational information* that is a candidate for import into a *professional educational record* after an *education professional* has confirmed its relevance to that *professional educational record*

EXAMPLE 1: Transfer credits - the credits from another institution being reviewed for equivalency A student transfers from another university, and the registrar evaluates course compatibility.

EXAMPLE 2: Exchange program results - the academic performance from an international program. A student completes a semester abroad, and their grades need conversion.

EXAMPLE 3: External certifications - the professional or industry-recognized credentials. A student submits a Coursera or Microsoft certification for credit towards a course.

EXAMPLE 4: Internship or work-based learning records documents verifying practical experience. A student

submits employer evaluations for academic credit in a work-integrated learning program.

EXAMPLE 5: Research contributions student-authored publications or research outcomes. A PhD student requests their published paper be added to their academic record.

EXAMPLE 6: Standardized test scores SAT, GRE, GMAT, or other external exams. A university imports TOEFL scores to determine language proficiency.

Table 130 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 142.

Table 130: Associations of *educational information for import* (tab:130)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational information</i>			
Association from			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational information for import</i>	is imported into	1 <i>professional educational record</i>
0..*	<i>non-ratified educational information</i>	becomes	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
1	<i>education professional</i>	has ratified	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>
0..*	<i>education provider activity</i>	generates	0..* <i>educational information for import</i>

Figure 142: Educational information for import (UML diagram)

12.17 Educational concern

Term: *educational concern* (*health concern*)

Definition: *educational record extract* that includes all *educational record components* associated with an *educational thread* for a specific concern

NOTE 1: A concern is gathered information to support continuity of learning for a *learner*. An *educational thread* can include *educational activities*, *education conditions*, healthcare activity planning, *educational activity management*, evaluations, and assessments. Thereby, all information needed for continuity of learning for an individual *learner* can be covered by an *educational concern*.

NOTE 2: *educational concerns* can be constructed to support continuity of learning for *educational processes*, *learning processes*, and accumulations/associations of *learning processes*. This means that concerns can

relate to *episode of learning support*, *educational contacts*, class periods, academic progress management, multiple subject management, etc.

EXAMPLE 1:Academic performance concern records related to a student’s academic struggles. A student is on academic probation, and faculty track grades, attendance, and interventions.

EXAMPLE 2:Special accommodations concern information on disability support, learning accommodations, or individualized education plans. A student with ADHD receives extended time on exams, and all accommodations are documented.

EXAMPLE 3:Interdisciplinary learning concern cross-course and multi-department learning records. A student pursuing a double major has a unified record of advising, credit approvals, and academic plans.

EXAMPLE 4:Academic misconduct concern documentation of plagiarism or cheating investigations. A student accused of plagiarism has records of hearings, evidence, and faculty decisions.

EXAMPLE 5:Internship and work-based learning concern record of professional learning experiences A student in a co-op program has employer evaluations, work reports, and academic reflections stored.

Table 131 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 143.

Table 131: Associations of *educational concern* (tab:131)

Specialization of		Generalization of	
<i>educational record extract</i>			
Association from	Association name	Association to	
1	<i>educational thread</i>	delineates	0..1 <i>educational concern</i>

Figure 143: Educational concern (UML diagram)

12.18 Educational information request

Term: *educational information request* (*healthcare information request*)

Definition: Request sent out by an *educational actor* to another *educational actor* for specific *educational information* needed for the provision of educational support to a *learner*

NOTE: To fulfil the request, a mandate to export personal information is needed.

EXAMPLE 1:Transcript request - requesting a student’s academic record from another institution. A student transfers from one university to another and submits a request for transcript evaluation.

EXAMPLE 2:Course equivalency request - requesting details about course content for credit transfer. A student applies for credit transfer, and the academic office requests course syllabi from the previous institution.

EXAMPLE 3:Academic progress report - requesting an updated performance report on a student.

EXAMPLE 4:Special Accommodations request requesting verification of disability or learning accommodations. A disability support office requests documentation from a previous institution to continue accommodations.

EXAMPLE 5:Exchange student information request requesting academic details for incoming or outgoing exchange students. A university requests course and language proficiency details from a partner institution for an incoming exchange student.

EXAMPLE 6:Internship verification request - requesting confirmation of work-based learning or internship completion. A student applying for graduation requests verification of an internship required for their degree.

EXAMPLE 7:Educational research data request - requesting anonymized student performance data for research purposes. A faculty member requests anonymized student retention data for an educational study.

Table 132 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 144.

Table 132: Associations of *educational information request* (tab:132)

Association from		Association name	Association to	
0..*	<i>educational information request</i>	is topic for	0..*	<i>educational record extract</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	sends out	0..*	<i>educational information request</i>
1	<i>educational actor</i>	receives	0..*	<i>educational information request</i>

Figure 144: Educational information request (UML diagram)

12.19 Certificate related to an educational matter

Term: *certificate related to an educational matter* (*certificate related to a healthcare matter*)

Definition: Official document issued by an *educational actor* attesting *educational matters* relating to a *learner*

EXAMPLE: Diploma, transcript, attendance certificate, educational achievement certificate

EXAMPLE 1: Diploma certifies completion of a degree program - Bachelor’s, Master’s, PhD. Used for employment, further studies, or professional licensing.

EXAMPLE 2: Attendance certificate confirms a student’s participation in a course or program.

EXAMPLE 3: Educational achievement certificate recognizes academic excellence or completion of a non-degree program.

EXAMPLE 4: Enrollment verification certificate confirms that a student is currently enrolled at the institution. Used for scholarships, insurance, or student loan applications.

EXAMPLE 5: Internship or practicum certificate confirms the completion of a practical learning experience. Needed for degree requirements, job applications, or licensure.

EXAMPLE 6: Thesis or dissertation defense certificate verifies that a student has successfully defended their thesis. Used for academic records and doctoral degree completion.

EXAMPLE 7: Honorary certificate recognizes outstanding contributions to academia or society. Awarded to distinguished individuals in education or research.

Table 133 lists the associations of this concept; a UML representation of the concept is shown in Figure 145.

Table 133: Associations of *certificate related to an educational matter* (tab:133)

Component of		Aggregation of	
		1..*	<i>educational record component</i>
Association from		Association name	Association to
0..*	<i>certificate related to an educational matter</i>	attests	1..* <i>educational matter</i>
0..*	<i>certificate related to an educational matter</i>	is issued by	1..* <i>educational actor</i>

Figure 145: Certificate related to an educational matter (UML diagram)

13 Conformance

References

- [1] J. A. Zachman, “The zachman framework for enterprise architecture,” *Primer for Enterprise Engineering and Manufacturing.[si]: Zachman International*, 2003.
- [2] D. Bjørner, *Software Engineering 3: Domains, requirements, and software design*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2006.
- [3] ISO, *13940:2015 Health informatics - system of concepts to support continuity of care*. Geneva. Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 2015.
- [4] —, *21001:2018 Educational organizations — Management systems for educational organizations — Requirements with guidance for use*. Geneva. Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 2018.
- [5] —, *ISO/IEC 2382:2015 Information technology — Vocabulary*. Geneva. Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 2015.
- [6] —, *ISO 10303-1:2024 Industrial automation systems and integration — Product data representation and exchange*. Geneva. Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 2024.
- [7] —, *ISO 13606-2:2019 Health informatics — Electronic health record communication*. Geneva. Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 2019.
- [8] —, *ISO/IEC 14776-151:2010 Information technology — Small Computer System Interface (SCSI)*. Geneva. Switzerland: International Organization for Standardization, 2010.